

Self-Organized Structures in Z-Pinch Plasmas

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General Description of This Work

This dissertation is concerned with the results of diagnostics, namely, the discussion and remarks about the manifestation and evolution of some self-organized and regular structures observed in mega-amperic gas discharges in the z-pinch devices S-300 in Moscow, a small device settled in Prague, and the PF-1000 in Warsaw, Poland. This work contains a list of figures (74), a list of tables (19), a notation list, with the most used symbols representing physical quantities or variables. This work is composed of 11 chapters. Chapters 1-5 conform the first part, and are intended to present the most relevant information of what was the scientific context on which this work falls within physics and introduce most of the relevant formulas and equations. Chapters 6-11 are the second and final part, corresponding to the analysis of the experimental results. Chapter 6 is meant for describing the actual experimental conditions and the data hence obtained. Chapters 7-10 correspond to the numerical and phenomenological evaluation of the experimental data. The final chapter summarizes the main conclusions. Appendix A contains a list of the 38 most used equations or physical relations. Most calculations were carried on in the programs Mathematica [1], and StarOffice V. 5.1 spreadsheets [2]. The thesis itself was processed with $\text{\TeX}$.

In the Department of Physics of the CTU the pinches have been being investigated for many years. The experimental background is oriented on diagnostic methods including Schlieren photography, Quadro camera diagnostics, X-ray diagnostics, interferometry measurements and streak camera, among others. The data obtained from these diagnostics were analyzed [3,4]. In Moscow since 1996, there was a series of experiments with the S-300 device [5], on which it was used among other diagnostic procedures, streak camera, from which the magnetic pressure could be calculated. In 1997 spirals surrounding the pinch were detected [3], like the one shown below. The fact that a very identifiable, recurrent,

geometrical structure appears in the z-pinches, has motivated to analyze the experimental data in a way that would cast light over this structure. In a previous research, analysis of the experimental data and diagnostics were done [3, 4]. Theoretical research has been done as well, developing the PIC (Particle in Cell) method and describing the main theoretical ideas about the pinch helicity [6], although is not part of this work. This work also includes analysis of experimental results, and the determination of some of the parameters which probably give rise to self-organization (mainly recurrent helical structures in the visible region of the electro-magnetic spectrum) and some regular structures (ringed cylinders in the X-Ray region of the electro-magnetic spectrum).

One of the observed spirals

Appendix 1 collects the used formulas.

Declaration of Originality

This dissertation contains the results of research carried out in the Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Department of Physics, Czech Technical University, between October, 1997 and July, 2000.

Excluding introductory section the research described in this dissertation is original unless where explicit reference (121 in overall) is made to the work of others. Some of this work was carried out in collaboration. The data for this work comes mostly from experiments done in the Kurchatov Institute, in Moscow, since 1996. I further state that no part of this dissertation or anything substantially the same has been submitted for any qualification other than the degree of Doctor of Philosophy at the Czech Technical University. Some of the research in this dissertation has been, or is to be, published.

The ideas on which this work is based come mostly from the following collaborations:

- December 1997-October 2000. Diverse collaborations with the department of physics at the Czech Technical University.

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- P. Kubeš, J. Kravárik, A. Ortiz- Tapia, L. Karpinski (June 29-July 3, 1998) **Generation of X-Radiation of a Rod Corona from a Small Magnetic Pinch**, in *Proceedings*

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- A. Ortiz-Tapia (May, 1999) **Particle-in-cell simulation**, in *Proceedings of Poster '99 3rd International Student Conference on Electrical Engineering*; Prague, Czech Republic.

- A. Ortiz-Tapia (February, 2000) **Magnetic field of the wire corona in MA Z-pinch**, in *Proceedings of Workshop 2000*; Prague, Czech republic.

- A. Ortiz-Tapia, P. Kubeš (2000) **Identification of the Governing Parameters of Self-Organizing Structures in Z-Pinch Plasmas**, in *Proceedings of the 19th Symposium on Plasma Physics and Technology*; Prague, Czech republic

- A. Ortiz-Tapia(October,2000) **Considerations about Self-Organization in Plasma Structures in Z-Pinch Discharges**, in *Proceedings of International Workshop on Dense Magnetized Plasmas IWDMP2000* ; Kudowa Zdroj, Poland.

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To All the People I Have Always Loved and Will Always Love

Eadem Mutata Resurgo "Though changed, I rise again the same"

Inscription and spiral on the Bernoulli monument

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Notation

MKS units will be used throughout this dissertation. The following symbols and abbreviations may be used. Several books were consulted for the make of this convention [7–18]

B	Magnetic Field
E	Electric Field
$\mathbb{P}$	Pressure Tensor
A	Amperes [Units of Current]
C	Coulomb [Units of Charge]
j	Current Density [A m^{-2}]
ρ	Charge Density [C m^{-3}]
T	Tesla [Unit of Magnetic Intensity]
B_φ	Azimuthal Magnetic Field [T]
B_Z	Axial Magnetic Field [T]
$\bar{B}_\varphi$	Average of the Azimuthal Magnetic Field [T]
$\bar{B}_Z$	Average of the Axial Magnetic Field
$\bar{B}_\varphi^2$	Square of the Average of the Poloidal Magnetic Field
$\bar{B}_Z^2$	Square of the Average of the Axial Magnetic Field
m^{-3}	Cubic Meters [Units of Volume]
m^2	Square Meters [Units of Area]
m	Meters [Units of Length]
K	Degree Kelvin [Units of Temperature]
T	Temperature [K]
eV	ElectronVolt $1.6 \times 10^{-19}\text{J}$ [as a Unit of Energy]
eV	ElectronVolt 11600 K [as a Unit of Temperature]
$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	Meters per Second [Units of Velocity/Speed]
J	Joule [Unit of Energy]
S.O.	Self-Organization (Also Self-Organized, etc.)
B_p	Poloidal Magnetic Field

B_T	Toroidal Magnetic Field
ε_0	Permittivity of Free Space 8.85×10^{-12} [A s/(V m)]
μ_0	Permeability of Free Space $4\pi \times 10^{-7}$ [H m ⁻¹]
η	Resistivity [Ohm meters]
n	Concentration of particles [m ⁻³]
n_e	Concentration of electrons [m ⁻³]
n_i	Concentration of ions [m ⁻³]
M	mass of the H ion 1.67×10^{-27} [Kg]
m	mass of the electron 9.109×10^{-31} [Kg]
M_{Al}	mass of the Al ion $27 \times 1.67 \times 10^{-27}$ [Kg]
e	Elementary Charge or Charge of Electron $\pm 1.602 \times 10^{-19}$ [C]
k	Boltzmann Constant 1.380658×10^{-23} [J/K]
γ	Conductivity [siemens · m ⁻¹]

Part I
Introductory Theory

Chapter 1

Plasma Physics

1.1 Definition

Plasma physics deals with all the phenomena that develops in a particular kind of gases, called plasma. Plasma is a quasi-neutral, ionized gas, which contains charged and neutral particles, and is able to show collective behavior [19–24]. The concept ”quasi-neutral” means that a plasma is able to screen out almost every electrical potential or field which would be on its interior. A plasma, however, contains charged particles and they can, during their motion, create local concentrations of positive or negative charge, which leads to the arise of an electric field. This field influences the motion of the particles at a distant position, which in turns gives rise to ”collective behavior”. Even if most of the fields are screened out, collective behavior of plasma can still be present out of a the small remaining electric field. Later we will learn that self-organization demands conditions a bit different from the ones that demands collective behavior [25]. Before plasma was studied on its own, it was considered within the framework of ionized gases [26].

1.2 Parameters that define a plasma

1.2.1 Debye Length λ_D

Debye length [19–21] is the distance of screening out of electrostatic fields in a plasma, and the number of particles in a Debye sphere is used for calculations related with the collective and self-organized behavior of particles in a plasma [27].

The Debye length is calculated as

$$\lambda_D = \left(\frac{\varepsilon_0 kT}{ne^2} \right)^{1/2} \quad (1.1)$$

Sometimes it is used as well the relation

$$\lambda_D = 7.4 \times 10^3 \left(\frac{kT}{n} \right)^{1/2} \quad (1.2)$$

kT together must be given in eV so that the result is in meters.

1.2.2 Number of Particles in Debye Sphere N_D

The number of particles in the Debye sphere [19, 20] can be calculated from the Debye length:

$$N_D = n \cdot \frac{4}{3} \pi \lambda_D^3 \quad (1.3)$$

1.2.3 Plasma Frequency

Plasma frequency is the natural frequency of oscillation of charged particles. It is indirectly proportional to the square root of the correspondent particle (electron or ion). Heavier particles hence have a lower frequency. The natural frequency of the ions corresponds to the expansion of magneto-acoustic waves, and the natural frequency of the electrons is related with the expansion of electro-magnetic waves [28].

For calculating the plasma frequency it is used the general formula for electrons [19]

$$\omega_{p_e} = \left(\frac{ne^2}{\epsilon m} \right)^{1/2} \quad (1.4)$$

or the hydrogen ions

$$\omega_{p_{ions}} = \left(\frac{ne^2}{\epsilon M} \right)^{1/2} \quad (1.5)$$

which for hydrogen can be expressed simply as [19]

$$\omega_p \approx 9\sqrt{n} \quad (1.6)$$

However Eq.(1.4) renders a result 6.26 times bigger than Eq.(1.6) (for electrons), and Eq.(1.5) (for protons) renders a result which is systematically 6.85 times smaller than Eq.(1.6). We realize however that the simplified formula $9\sqrt{n}$ represents the geometric mean of the plasma frequency of electrons and the plasma frequency of ions

$$\omega_p \approx \sqrt{\omega_{p_e} \times \omega_{p_i}} \quad (1.7)$$

We can use the geometric mean 1.7 for obtaining a simplified, approximate collective formula for both electrons and ions, which in the case of Al is Eq.(1.8)

$$\omega_{p_{Al}} = 4\sqrt{n} \quad (1.8)$$

1.2.4 Plasma Frequency Times Collision Time $\omega\tau$

Moreover [19, 20], if ω is the frequency of typical plasma oscillations and τ is the mean time between collisions with neutral atoms, we require that $\omega\tau > 1$. We also require that

$\lambda_D \ll L$, where L are the dimensions of the system. This means that whenever local concentrations of charge arise or external potentials are introduced into the system, these are shielded out in a distance short compared with L , leaving the bulk of the plasma free of large electric potentials or fields. So the plasma should be dense enough that $\lambda_D \ll L$. Finally, in order to show self-organizing structures, $N_D < 1$. These are characteristics of plasmas which are non-ideal, with high potential energy, non-Debye, quantum or strongly auto-correlated [29].

1.3 Material Constants in a Plasma

1.3.1 Alfvén Velocity

An Alfvén wave is a plasma wave generated by ions oscillating about their equilibrium positions [30]. The origin of this movement comes from $\mathbf{B}$ acting upon the ions, and the velocity with which they displace is called "Alfvén velocity", which is calculated using Eq.(1.9) [19].

$$v_A = \frac{B}{(\mu_0 \rho_{Al})^{1/2}} \quad (1.9)$$

where ρ_{Al} was calculated from $n \times M_{Al}$.

In Chap.(9) we shall use Alfvén velocity for the evaluation of diverse magnetic parameters of S.O. structures.

1.3.2 Conductivity (Resistivity)

The conductivity in a plasma can be calculated using the inverse of the Spitzer formula (meant for calculation of resistivity) [19]:

$$\eta \approx \frac{e^2 m^{1/2}}{16\pi\epsilon_0^2 (kT_e)^{3/2}} \cdot \ln \Lambda \quad (1.10)$$

where $\ln \Lambda$ is the Coulomb logarithm and $\Lambda = |\lambda_D/r_0|$, being r_0 the *collision parameter* which is calculated as [19]

$$r_0 = \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 m v_A^2}, \quad (1.11)$$

and we have used v_A , the alfvén velocity as in Eq.(1.9) [19], since it is the closest to the velocity of expansion of the corona diameter (compare the results of Sec.(6.2) with Sec.(8.6).

1.4 Importance of the Study of Plasmas

1.4.1 Ubiquity of Plasmas

First of all, because plasma is almost everywhere in the visible universe [19, 28, 31], plasma is obviously of scientific interest.

According to the Saha equation, which tells us the amount of ionization to be expected in a gas in thermal equilibrium:

$$\frac{n_i}{n_n} \approx 2.4 \times 10^{15} \frac{T^{3/2}}{n_i} e^{-U_i/kT}$$

where n_n is the density of neutral atoms, and U_i is the ionization energy of the gas, i.e., the number of joules required to remove the outermost electron from an atom. For ordinary air at room temperature, we may take $n_n \approx 3 \times 10^{25} \text{m}^{-3}$, $T \approx 300\text{K}$, and $U_i = 14.5 \text{eV}$ (for nitrogen). Then, the fractional ionization predicted by the Saha equation is

$$\frac{n_i}{n_n} \approx 10^{-122}$$

As the temperature is raised, the degree of ionization remains low until U_i is only a few times kT . Then n_i/n_n rises abruptly, and the gas is in a plasma state. Plasma, then exists naturally in all the bodies with temperatures of millions of degrees and because of the fact that a good percentage of the astronomical bodies are at those temperatures, plasma is of primary interest for the understanding of the universe. For example the original dipole field of the planets, in particular the Earth, is deformed by the interaction with the Solar wind, until acquiring the characteristic shape of the magnetosphaera. Quite close to the planets there is (in general) co-rotating the plasmosphaera. Towards the Sun there is a shock wave, on which there with a jump there is a change in the parameters of the Solar wind. In a direction away from the Sun, a plasma tail is elongated. The plasma system acts as a defense layer in the magnetosphaera (Fig.(1.1)) [28].

Figure 1.1: **Magnetosphaera of Earth.** In the co-rotating plasmosphaera the particle's temperature is 1 eV, in the plasma tail 1 to 10 keV, with a concentration of particles of $0.5 \times 10^6 \text{m}^{-3}$. The plasma tail is elongated as much as 100 times Earth's radius, with a thickness of 20 Earth's radius. The protection layer of the magnetosphaera separates the magnetic field of Earth from its surroundings, and it has a particle concentration of $1 \times 10^6 \text{m}^{-3}$ [28].

In the polar regions of Earth the caught charged particles create a characteristic dis-

charge sheet -the polar shine, in Latin *aurora Borealis* (Fig.(1.2)). The current flows in these sheets along the field lines of the magnetic field of the planets, and is the so-called *Birkeland current* [28].

Figure 1.2: Northern Shine (Aurora Borealis). (a) As seen by a terrestrial observer [32]. (b) Seen from the space [33]

1.4.2 Applicability of Plasmas

The second reason for studying plasmas is its applications [19–23, 28]. Among them, very important is the production of thermonuclear energy [34]. In 1952 it was proposed for the first time that the hydrogen bomb fusion reaction could be controlled to make a reactor. The principal reactions, which involve deuterium (D) and tritium (T) atoms, are as follows:

The cross sections for these fusion reactions are appreciable only for incident energies above 10 keV. Accelerated beams of deuterons bombarding a target will not work, because

most of the deuterons will lose their energy by scattering before undergoing a fusion reaction. It is necessary to create a plasma in which the thermal energies are in the 10-keV range. The goal is to get a Maxwellian plasma, whose fast particles in the tail of the velocity distribution would enter fusion reaction. The Lawson's criterion is a condition so that from the fusion reaction would come more energy than the necessary to heat the plasma. The fulfillment of the condition is given by the confinement time and the density of the plasma. The minimal value needed for the reaction deuterium-tritium is around $10^{20}\text{m}^{-3}\text{s}$ and for the reaction deuterium-deuterium is around $10^{22}\text{m}^{-3}\text{s}$. In this last reaction it is possible to produce electrical energy directly, without a thermal intermediary (steam generation which could be used to rotate a dynamo), and there would be no radiation [35]. It is clear, however, that it is supposed to be a higher density and temperature. One possibility out of a few how to get those conditions is the Z-pinch [36–38].

Chapter 2

Pinch

2.1 Definition

Pinches are one of the most common structures in both space and laboratory plasma [19, 23, 31]. For example, the conductive channel of a lightning is a pinch [28], and for humans is probably the best example of plasma (Fig.(2.1)). Some typical parameters of the lightning are (on Earth):

- Average diameter of the conductive channel $\approx 5 \times 10^{-2}$ m
- Channel length $\approx 3 \times 10^3$ m
- Current ≈ 200 kA
- Temperature $\approx 3 \times 10^4$ K
- Life-time $\approx 10^{-4}$ s
- Speed of movement ≈ 0.1 c (that is $3 \times 10^6 \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)
- Energy $\approx 6 \times 10^8$ J
- Volume from which the charge is collected $\approx 10^{12} \text{m}^{-3}$

Pinch [9, 19] is understood as plasma, through which flows such a heavy current, that creates its own magnetic field, which at the same time heats the plasma. The main problem of the pinch are the instabilities which disperse the contracted plasma [37, 40].

Figure 2.1: Lightning as an example of a pinch [28]. Archive photo from the NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, in U.S.A.) [39]

2.2 Basic Mechanism of Pinch Generation

Consider the following simple problem, which illustrates the action of the magnetic pressure [9].

Suppose we had two long, straight, parallel conductors separated by a distance r and carrying currents I and I' , respectively, in the same direction, and one over the other. Each conductor lies in the magnetic field set up by the other, so each experiences a force. The magnitude of the $\mathbf{B}$ vector at the upper conductor is

$$B = \frac{\mu I}{2\pi r}. \quad (2.1)$$

The force on a length L of the upper conductor is

$$F = I'LB = \frac{\mu_0 II'L}{2\pi r},$$

and the force *per unit length* F/L is

$$\frac{F}{L} = \frac{\mu_0 II'}{2\pi r}.$$

The right-hand rule would show that the direction of the force on the upper conductor is downward. The current in the upper conductor also sets upon a field at the position

of the lower one. Two successive applications of the right-hand rule show that the force on the lower conductor is upward. Thus two parallel conductors carrying current in the same direction attract each other. Mutual forces of attraction exist not only between wires carrying currents in the same direction, but also between the longitudinal elements of a single current-carrying conductor. If the conductor is a liquid or an ionized gas (and in particular a plasma), these forces result in a constriction of the conductor, as if its surface were acted on by an external, inward pressure. The constriction of the conductor is called the pinch effect. The high temperature produced by the pinch effect in a plasma has been used in one technique to bring about nuclear fusion [9].

2.3 Bennett condition

It is more correct to explain the pinch adding the Bennett condition for pinching, which says that the magnetic pressure equals the dynamic pressure at equilibrium, i.e.

$$\frac{\bar{B}_\varphi^2}{2\mu_0} = nkT \quad (2.2)$$

We have assumed (and we will assume throughout all this work) in Eq.(2.2) that pressure is isotropic, i.e., that the tensor of pressure $\mathbb{P}$ can be reduced to a scalar composed of the sum of pressures coming from ions and electrons, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} p &= \sum_{i,e} n_{i,e} kT_{i,e} \\ &= nkT \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

In general, however, $\mathbb{P}$ is indeed a tensor, for it is influenced by the action of the magnetic

fields [14].

2.4 Spirals due to B_Z

For the description of the spirals observed we have to consider the existence of an axial magnetic field, whose outward pressure pulls the pinch into a spiral, and eventually also contributes to the destruction of the Z-pinch:

$$\frac{\bar{B}_\phi^2}{2\mu_0} = nkT + \frac{\bar{B}_Z^2}{2\mu_0} \tag{2.4}$$

The configuration for a Z-pinch, with the Bennett condition for pinching can be seen in Fig.(2.2(a)). The axial magnetic field generated by the pinch itself, together with the spiral due to the action of both axial and azimuthal magnetic fields is depicted in Fig.(2.2(b)):

Figure 2.2: (a) Bennett pinch. (b) Pinch with the pressures that may lead to an spiral (for clarity, in the figure is not indicated the Pressure by B_Z)

2.5 Pinch Types

2.5.1 Z-Pinch

Pinch discharges exist in several fashions. The one studied in this work is the Z-pinch of which extensive literature can be found [37]. The fiber Z-pinch discharge is studied in many laboratories mainly for its intensive X-ray emission and for fusion research.

The basic set-up consists of a single wire, or a wire array which connects the anode and cathode, and through which flows a high current pulse.

Some pictures of Z-pinch as seen with a pinhole camera are in Fig.(2.3), from a discharge developed in the Sandia National Laboratories [41].

Figure 2.3: (a) At Sandia laboratories, May 97. Photograph of annular wire array hardware for 17th radiation shot (PBFA Z Shot 26. Wires are tensioned with copper weights. One of the 240 wires was lost during assembly. Support posts are removed after installation in PBFA Z. Pinhole camera image of imploded plasma stagnated on axis for shot. Total radiated energy was 1.85 MJ, peak x-ray power was ~ 160 TW, and minimum pinch diameter was ~ 1 mm. (b) February 1998. The x-ray images on Shot 180 (right image) show the achievement of the tightest pinch yet on Z (1 mm diameter). The x-ray data also indicate that the inner array expands somewhat before the inner edge of the outer array reaches the inner array. The low (2.5-kA) current measured per inner wire with a Bdot monitor implies that most of this inner array expansion is not from current preheat and is more likely caused by radiation preheat. Pinhole images on nested shot 180 at 1 ns intervals. Pinch compression 40:1. [41]

2.5.2 Plasma Focus

The pinch principle, however, can be seen in other types of devices, like the plasma focus and the theta pinch. The basic set-up for a plasma focus is a wire which ends up one of the electrodes, and to which converges the pulsed, high-current discharge. A plasma focus discharge typically has an umbrella-like geometry, as it can be seen in Fig.(2.4).

Figure 2.4: Scheme of the principle for plasma focus [28]

Fig.(2.5(a)) and Fig.(2.5(b)) depict plasma focus as seen from shadowgraphy and Schlieren camera [42].

Figure 2.5: (a) Shadowgram picture of Speed HHW Dusseldorf Focus Group 1985. Time evolution of the POSEIDON focus plasma and neutron emission [42]. (b) Speed HHU Dusseldorf Focus Group 1985. Dark Schlieren pictures of two SPEED 1 plasma focus discharges at different filling pressures: 6×10^2 Pa upper, 8×10^2 Pa lower set. High pressure discharges tend to $m=0$ instability development while lower pressures result in fairly stable pinches [42].

2.6 Pinch Instabilities

The main problem of pinch plasmas is the great diversity of instabilities that is liable to [35, 43, 44]. Most of the instabilities are complex enough to be tangent to highly mathematical theories [45–49]. Some of the most important instabilities are the magneto-hydrodynamic ones [28, 37], and the Rayleigh-Taylor [37]. In Fig.(2.6) we can see the MHD instabilities, and in Fig.(2.7) we may appreciate the Rayleigh-Taylor ones. The last figures were obtained in the Magpie device with the Schlieren technique [50]. It is clear that a great interest of general Z-pinch investigation is focused on Z-pinch stability, i.e., on the suppression of development of instabilities [37].

Figure 2.6: (a) $m=0$ instability. (b) $m=1$ instability [28]

2.6.1 Magneto-hydrodynamic Turbulence

The study of magneto-hydrodynamic turbulence, i.e., the study of the interaction between a magnetic field and the turbulent motions of an electrically-conducting fluid, was first undertaken in connection with the implied existence of an interstellar magnetic field. The interaction between the velocity and magnetic fields results in a transfer of energy between the kinetic and magnetic spectra, and it is thought that the interstellar magnetic field is

Figure 2.7: 300 ps shadowgrams of central cm of pinch, illustrating the Rayleigh-Taylor (advanced $m=0$) instability, taken in the Magpie device at the Imperial College in London, at time of hot spot formation. [50]. (a) 14 ns. (b) 42 ns

maintained by a "dynamo" action from turbulence in the interstellar gas [48].

Turbulence is the effect which plays an important role during implosion. Pinched plasma reaches a velocity of $10^4 - 10^6 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and surpasses several times the critical Alfvén velocity. As a consequence of the fluctuations in particle density, velocity, current, pressure and an unstable character of the movement, there is a generation of whirlpools [35]. During their creation the kinetic translational energy density overcomes the magnetic energy density. Whirlpools in plasma are like conductive loops with moving charges within an external magnetic field and they induce currents which in turn generate an own magnetic field with a dipole character. The dipole character of the turbulence is projected through diamagnetism, during which the original magnetic field overtakes turbulence and the effect of forces is projected radially and axially, by mutual attraction of whirlpools [35].

Turbulent structures are characterized by a low dissipation of energy. The reasons can

be several; the most important could be:

- The magnetic field overtaking of whirlpools, which isolate the individual whirlpools mutually.
- Mutual interaction of electron and ion components, for the Coulomb effective cross-section for collisions is reduced with the increase of mutual velocities.
- A third factor can be the existence of electrical double-layers. An electrical double-layer is created as a consequence of the difference of size of the Larmor radius and weight of electrons and ions. The distance between layers corresponds to the Debye radius [35].

2.6.2 Time Evolution of the Magnetic Field

We can have Maxwell's equation in several representations [49], but for our purposes it is sufficient that we take the MKS-differential form [14]. From that set of equations we may deduce a convenient formula for the evolution of the magnetic field in time. In concrete we depart from the equations

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = -\nabla \times \mathbf{E}$$

and

$$\mathbf{j} = \gamma(\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B})$$

which we can rearrange as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} &= -\nabla \times \mathbf{E} \\ &= -\nabla \times \left[\frac{\mathbf{j}}{\gamma} - \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} \right] \\ &= \nabla \times [\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}] - \frac{1}{\gamma\mu_0} \nabla \times [\nabla \times \mathbf{B}] \\ &= \nabla \times [\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}] + \frac{1}{\gamma\mu_0} \Delta \mathbf{B} - \frac{1}{\gamma\mu_0} \nabla \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} \end{aligned}$$

(2.5)

therefore we can see that it is valid to say that

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times [\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}] + \frac{1}{\gamma \mu_0} \Delta \mathbf{B} \quad (2.6)$$

which is the equation of change of the magnetic field in a conductive environment.

For slow velocities or small conductivity Eq.2.6 has the form

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\gamma \mu_0} \Delta \mathbf{B} \quad (2.7)$$

”The time change of the magnetic field is proportional to the spatial decrease of the gradient of the magnetic field”.

Diffusion time

Using Eq. 2.7 and taking finite changes in time, space and magnetic field, we may write

$$\frac{\Delta \mathbf{B}}{\Delta t} = \frac{1}{\gamma \mu_0} \cdot \frac{\Delta \mathbf{B}}{L^2}$$

where L is the characteristic dimension of the region. We can deduce therefore the diffusion time (since $\Delta B \rightarrow 0$ as $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$)

$$\Delta t = \mu \gamma L^2 \quad (2.8)$$

Freezing of the Magnetic Lines into the Plasma

In the case of high conductivity the first member of Eq.2.6 dominates and we obtain the equation

$$\frac{\Delta \mathbf{B}}{\Delta t} = \nabla \times [\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}] \quad (2.9)$$

We can interpret Eq.(2.9) that plasma which flows perpendicular to the magnetic lines, takes them and somehow deforms them into spirals. The time required for this sort of deformation is

$$\frac{\Delta B}{\Delta t} = \frac{VB}{L} \quad (2.10)$$

where V is the characteristic velocity of the plasma (generally in here is considered the Alfvén velocity) [27], and L is the characteristic dimension of the plasma (or rather the characteristic dimension of the plasma process being analyzed [27]). From Eq.(2.10) we can express (since $\Delta B \rightarrow 0$ as $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$)

$$\Delta t = \frac{L}{V} \quad (2.11)$$

The ratio of the magnetic diffusion and the freezing of magnetic lines into plasma is

$$R_M = \mu\gamma VL \quad (2.12)$$

Where R_M is called the Reynold's magnetic number. In the case that $R_M \gg 1$ the eddies deformation of $\mathbf{B}$ dominates and the magnetic field holds the plasma in an action called "freezing of the magnetic lines into plasma". When $R_M \ll 1$ it is the diffusion term which dominates. For self-organization it is important that the magnetic energy density be high enough, so that it may dominate over kinetic energy density [27].

Chapter 3

Self-Organized Structures

3.1 Definition of Self-Organization

The evolution of a system into an organized form in the absence of external constraints [51]. A move from a large region of state space to a persistent smaller one, under the control of the system itself. Organization means the arrangement of parts in such a way as to be non-random. The restriction of the options available to a system in such a way as to confine it to a small volume of its state space. Usually self-organization is opposed to a reductionist point of view, i.e., it opposes to explain the evolution of a system purely on the basis of the physical laws that started its evolution, claiming that new properties appear during the evolution, which in turn influence the evolution of the system itself [51–58]. Physically speaking, self-organization occurs due to long-range correlations [27, 59].

3.2 Attractor

3.2.1 Definition of Attractor

A preferred position for the system, such that if the system is started from another state it will evolve until it arrives at the attractor, and will then stay there in the absence of other factors. An attractor can be a point (e.g. the center of a bowl containing a ball), a regular

path (e.g. a planetary orbit), a complex series of states (e.g. the metabolism of a cell) or an infinite sequence (called a strange attractor). All specify a restricted volume of state space. The area of state space that leads to an attractor is called its basin of attraction [51–58].

3.2.2 Relationship Between Attractors and Self-Organization

Any system that moves to a fixed structure can be said to be drawn to an attractor (in our case the attractor is a force-free structure, namely, the helical, toroidal or ball structures) . A complex system can have many attractors and these can alter with changes to the system interconnections (mutations). Studying self-organization is equivalent to investigating the attractors of the system, their form and dynamics [51–57].

3.3 Percolation and its Relation to Self-Organized-Criticality (SOC)

Percolation is an arrangement of parts (usually visualized as a matrix) such that a property can arise that connects the opposite sides of the structure. This can be regarded as making a path in a disconnected matrix or making an obstruction in a fully connected one. The boundary at which the system goes from disconnected to connected is a sudden one, a step or phase change in the properties of the system. This is the same boundary that we arrive at in SOC. The main feature is that at this boundary a system has a correlation length that just spans the entire system, with a power law distribution of shorter lengths [51–53, 60].

3.4 Power Laws

3.4.1 Definition of Power Law

We plot the logarithm of the number of times a certain property value is found against the log of the value itself. If the result is a straight line then we have a power law. Essentially what we are saying is that there is a distribution of results such that the larger the effect the less frequently it is seen. A good example is earthquake activity where many small quakes are seen but few large ones, the Richter scale is based upon such a law. A system subject to power law dynamics exhibits the same structure over all scales. This self-similarity or scale independent (fractal) behavior is typical of self-organizing systems [51–53, 60–62].

3.4.2 Relationship of Power Laws and Fractals with Chaos

In nonlinear studies we find much structure for very simple systems, as seen in the self-similar structure of fractals and the bifurcation structure seen in chaotic systems. This form of system exhibits complex behavior from simple rules. In contrast, for self-organizing systems we have complex assemblies generating simple emergent behavior, so in essence the two concepts are complementary. Moreover the orientation of the spirals observed can be called "chaotic" in the sense of unpredictability, described elsewhere in detail [48, 56, 63–66], then it comes the self-organized spiral [27]. That means both chaotic and self-organized processes can be found in a plasma [67, 68], mostly because of its statistical nature [24, 69–78].

3.5 Self-Organized Structures in Plasma

3.5.1 General Features of S.O. in Plasmas

The following are general characteristics around self-organization in plasmas:

- Energy pumping into the system, entropy (superfluity) expulsion, and nonlinearity are the three key processes governing self-organization [54, 79].

- Non-linear, self-regulating processes with finite amplitude lead to self organization in plasmas [55]. By finite amplitude is understood a finite displacement or movement from an assumed equilibrium position [9].

Structural Model of S.O.

Sato has proposed a general scenario of self-organization for plasmas [54, 79], whose steps are briefly described below. An schematic version of these steps can be followed in Fig.(3.1)

(1) *Open System* Income of electric energy, non-linear system and outcome of particles and radiation

(2) *Pumping-in of free energy* Electric energy transforms into thermal energy due to Joule heating and into kinetic energy, due to the Lorenz force ($\mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{B}$)

(3) *The plasma becomes unstable* Development of MHD instabilities

(4) *Inception of a critical stage* Generation of turbulent structures and stochastic magnetic fields rise of temperature and very fast energy conversions

(5) *Possibility of bifurcation* Either destruction or self-organization. There is a suppression of the development of instabilities. The causes can be high plasma density, higher magnetic energy density than kinetic energy, self-generated through dynamo processes, and electrostatic energy density higher than the kinetic energy. The last one can be interpreted in the light of non-ideality, for a small number of particles in the Debye sphere indicates a non-ideal plasma, with an electrostatic energy higher than the kinetic energy [55].

(6) *Anomalous production of entropy* Growth of chaos, i.e., rise of plasma temperature due to energy transformations.

(7) *Expulsion of the Produced Entropy and Emergence of Self-Organization* The entropy

is decreased by two main processes: particle expulsion and energy radiated (assuming for example the Stephan-Boltzmann law). Once the entropy has been expelled, the emergence of self-organized structures may occur.

(8) *Destruction of the Self-Organized Structures* Plasma explosion probably caused by the dissipation of the magnetic field from the dense plasma and the release of its magnetic confinement.

Figure 3.1: Scheme of self-organization

3.5.2 Self-Organization in Plasmas Related with this Work

The appearance of geometrical, persistent patterns in dense z-pinch plasmas, for example helical [80], ball [81], toroidal [81] and filamentary [60] structures present from laboratory plasmas to scales of the order of entire galaxies were detected, which might behave similarly to a magneto-hydrodynamic dynamo, and they have probably fractal dimension [60]. By helical (or spiral) we mean any plasma structure which is the result of a recursive and a progressive process [82]. It will be evident in forthcoming figures that we need this broad definition for spirals have been observed by means of different methods of diagnostics. These recurrent geometrical structures have been studied intensely as percolating networks, and fine structure of the magnetic field with the collective name of "heteromacs" [60, 83–86]. These structures occur due to long-range, non-linear space correlations between the set

of particles inside the plasma [54, 60], and pumping-in of free energy and expulsion of entropy [54]. Moreover, Kadomchev [55] suggests that the azimuthal magnetic field B_φ generated by the initial current, in turns generates a second current, which in turns generates an axial magnetic field B_Z . Both magnetic fields, then, would generate the observed spiral. If the spiral eventually disperses, it is probably because the poloidal magnetic field (expulsive) is stronger than the compressive toroidal magnetic field [27, 60]. Kulik [29] suggests the following criteria for non-ideal plasmas (our plasmas are assumed non-ideal and this leading to self-organization into helical, toroidal and ball structures):

3.6 Non-Ideality and S.O.

For a plasma to be non-ideal, the ratio of electrical potential energy between particles to kinetic energy should be about above 1:

$$\gamma = \bar{U}/\bar{E} > 1$$

which can be written as

$$\gamma = e^2 n_e^{1/3} / kT > 1 \quad (3.1)$$

where e is the charge of the electron, n_e is the concentration of electrons, k is the Boltzmann's constant and T is the temperature in Kelvins.

Let

$$\bar{\lambda} = h/(2\pi m kT)^{1/2}$$

be the de Broglie length. Let moreover

$$A = \bar{\lambda} n^{1/3}$$

then it should be true that $A\gamma^2 > 1$ about above one.

Also, let

$$\zeta = \frac{1}{6} \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda_D kT}{e^2} \right) \quad (3.2)$$

Now, suppose we graphicated the temperature (x axis) against the concentration of electrons (y axis). Then, in the zone between $\zeta = 1$ and $\gamma = 1$ we would have a non-ideal plasma.

During pinch compression, non-ideality arises [35]. From the conditions inside the pinch, the number of particles in the Debye sphere < 1 and the Debye length is comparable with the distance between particles and the de Broglie wavelength of the electron. The electromagnetic energy is at least the same size as the thermal energy nkT . This characteristics make possible the generation of collective behavior in the electron component of a plasma, where even macroscopic quantum effects can be projected [35].

For non-ideality it is also important an intensive escape of energy radiated from the plasma, by which a low temperature in a dense plasma is kept [35].

3.7 Magnetic Energy Density and S.O.

Magnetic Energy density plays a fundamental role for self-organization. It is when $\rho(\mathbf{B}) > nkT$ when self-organization may occur. It is also important that this magnetic energy density is kept for longer time than the diffusion time of the magnetic field. We have found that this last statement implies that the conductivity in the plasmas analyzed in this work is higher than the calculated using Spitzer formula (see Sec.(9.4.2)).

Chapter 4

Mechanisms of Generation of B_φ and B_Z

4.1 Initial Generation of B_φ

From the law of Biot-Savart [9]

$$\mathbf{B} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{I d\mathbf{l} \times \hat{r}}{r^2} \quad (4.1)$$

we can find the total magnetic field $\mathbf{B}$ at any point in space due to the current in a complete circuit, by integrating Eq.4.1:

$$\mathbf{B} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \int \frac{I d\mathbf{l} \times \hat{r}}{r^2} \quad (4.2)$$

For the particular case of a long, straight conductor, as in the case of the initial current flowing through a wire in a Z-pinch device, Eq. 4.2 can be further evaluated to obtain

$$B_\varphi = \frac{\mu_0 I_z}{2\pi r} \quad (4.3)$$

we have obtained an expression which tell us the relationship between the initial axial current I_z and its consequent magnetic azimuthal field B_φ .

4.2 Dynamo Theory

4.2.1 Earth's Magnetic Field

It can be said that the theoretical basis for studying the generation of magnetic fields $B_\phi B_Z$ in Z-pinch is closely connected (by analogy of behavior) with the study of the generation of the Earth's magnetic field [65, 87–89]. Roughly speaking the Earth's magnetic field should have faded away hundreds of millions of years ago. The fact that there is still a magnetic field, and that it has a consistently identified quasi-periodical dynamic, lead to a closer physic-mathematical study of it, and it came that it is the rotations in Earth's magma that generate the Earth's magnetic field, like a dynamo [65] we can see in Fig.(4.1) the magnetic dipole of Earth [28, 79].

The structure of the magnetic field has been studied as well for the dynamo effect [14, 87, 90], and its relation to self-organization [91]. The dynamo effect roughly speaking deals with the generation of magnetic fields by moving fluids above the Curie temperature [87]. Plasmas are well above the Curie temperature [19], and yet, they possess an own magnetic field, due to the movement of electrical currents [14, 89].

4.2.2 Rikitake's Dynamo

The Rikitake's dynamo [65] is meant to model the change in polarity of the Earth's magnetic field (Fig.(4.2(a))). The set of equations that describe Rikitake's dynamo are

Figure 4.1: a) The magnetic field of Earth [28], b) (Simulation) Well-organized, magnetic cyclonic (black) and anti-cyclonic (white) columns along the rotation axis magma inside the Earth [79]

$$L\dot{I}_1 + RI_1 = M\Omega_1 I_1,$$

$$L\dot{I}_2 + RI_2 = M\Omega_2 I_2,$$

$$C\dot{\Omega}_1 = G - MI_1 I_2,$$

$$C\dot{\Omega}_2 = G - MI_1 I_2$$

(4.4)

where L is the induction of the dynamo, R is the resistance of each dynamo including the connections between them, M is the total mutual induction, C is the moment of inertia of the dynamo with respect to their axis and G is the pair of forces applied to this axis.

Eq.(4.4) are not mutually independent, for $\dot{\Omega}_1 - \dot{\Omega}_2 = 0$; the quantity $\Omega_1 - \Omega_2 = (GL/CM)^{1/2} = A$ is therefore the integral motion of the former.

In the system of equations 4.4 there are two kinds of time measures. The first, which we consider "mechanical time measure" τ_m , which gives the time within whose evolution

the dynamo reaches an angular velocity as a result of the pair of forces G in the absence of the Lorenz force's "typical" value R/M , hence $\tau_m = CR/GM$. The second time measure can be called "time of electro-magnetic diffusion" τ_e . If the disks are stopped within a given value of the magnetic field, then this field according to the first and second equation of the system 4.4 will vanish after the achievement of the characteristic time of order $\tau_e = L/R$. The ratio $\tau_m/\tau_e = CR^2/GLM = \mu^2$ can be chosen as the driving parameter of the system, and renders the ratio of accumulated mechanical energy to the accumulated electro-magnetic energy.

If now we are to measure the time t in units $(\tau_e\tau_m)^{1/2}$, the fluxes I_1, I_2 in units $(G/M)^{(1/2)}$ and the angular velocities Ω_1, Ω_2 in units $(GL/CM)^{1/2}$, then, shall we set $L_i = (G/M)^{1/2}X_i, \Omega_i = (GL/CM)^{1/2}Y_i, i = 1, 2$, we get for the integral motion the expression $A = Y_1 - Y_2$ and 4.4 can be expressed adimensionally as

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{X}_1 + \mu X_1 &= Y X_2, \\ \dot{X}_2 + \mu X_2 &= (Y - A) X_1, \\ \dot{Y} &= 1 - X_1 X_2\end{aligned}\tag{4.5}$$

The set of equations (4.5) can be plotted using the Euler method for integration and the initial conditions

The result can be observed in Fig.(4.2(b))

Figure 4.2: (a) Rikitake's dynamo, meant to model the change in polarity of the Earth's magnetic field. The disks move with an angular velocity Ω_1 , Ω_2 , in the magnetic field generated by two loops with currents I_1 , I_2 , with a resultant pair of forces $\mathbf{G}$. (b) Spiral obtained with the set of equations 4.5. The initial conditions were $x_1 = 1$, $y = x_1$, $x_2 = x_1$, $\mu = 1$, $K = 2$, $A = \mu \times (K^2 - K^{-2})$, $dt = .0001$ using 3×10^5 time-steps.

4.3 The α effect

The alpha effect is at the heart of modern dynamo theory. It essentially provides an obvious means whereby the 'dynamo cycle' $\mathbf{B}_p \xrightarrow{\alpha} \mathbf{B}_T$ may be completed [87].

Let us mark the dimensions of random influences in plasma as l_0 , the ion wavelength as a and the global dimension of the plasma as L . Let the relation $l_0 \ll a \ll L$ be valid. Similarly we can do for the time measure shall we mark T for the global time measure, t_0 the fluctuations' time measure and τ the mean time measure. Let the inequality for time $t_0 \ll \tau \ll T$ be valid directly.

For a mean, slowly-changing value of velocity $\mathbf{U}$ and a magnetic field $\mathbf{B}$, it is possible to deduce the relations:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{U}(x, t) &= \mathbf{U}_0(x, t) + \mathbf{u}(x, t) \langle \mathbf{u} \rangle = 0 \\
\mathbf{B}(x, t) &= \mathbf{B}_0(x, t) + \mathbf{b}(x, t) \langle \mathbf{b} \rangle = 0
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.6}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}_0}{\partial t} &= \nabla \times (\mathbf{U}_0 \times \mathbf{B}_0) + \nabla \times \varepsilon + \lambda \Delta \mathbf{B}_0 \\
\frac{\partial \mathbf{b}_0}{\partial t} &= \nabla \times (\mathbf{U}_0 \times \mathbf{b}) + \nabla \times (\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B}_0) + \nabla \times \mathbf{G} \lambda \Delta \mathbf{b}
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.7}$$

where

$$\varepsilon = \langle \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{b} \rangle, \mathbf{G} = \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{b} - \langle \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{b} \rangle
\tag{4.8}$$

The source of fluctuations of the magnetic field $\mathbf{b}$ is the expression $\nabla \times \langle \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B}_0 \rangle$. Since the dependency of the field ε to the field $\mathbf{B}_0$ is almost linear, it is possible to express the former as:

$$\varepsilon_i = \alpha_{ij} B_{0j} + \beta_{ijk} \frac{\partial B_{0j}}{\partial x_k} + \dots$$

α_{ij} , β_{ijk} are pseudo-tensors, because ε is a polar vector and $\mathbf{B}_0$ is an axial vector. Let us concentrate in the first member of the Taylor expansion

$$\varepsilon_i^{(0)} = \alpha_{ij} B_{0j}.$$

The tensor α_{ij} can be decomposed in a symmetric and an antisymmetric part:

$$\alpha_{ij} = \alpha_{ij}^{(s)} - \varepsilon_{ijk} a_k$$

Then we have

$$\varepsilon_i^{(0)} = \alpha_{ij}^{(s)} B_{0j} + (\mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{B}_0)$$

It is evident that the asymmetric part created a supplementary vector $\mathbf{a}$, a kind of mean velocity, which actuates upon $\mathbf{B}_0$ and creates together with the real mean velocity $\mathbf{U}_0$ an effective mean velocity

$$\mathbf{U}_0 + \mathbf{a}.$$

For $\varepsilon^{(0)} = \alpha B_0$ and with the Ohm law we can obtain:

$$\mathbf{j} = \sigma \varepsilon^{(0)} = \sigma \alpha \mathbf{B}_0$$

The shown induced current $\mathbf{j}$ flowing along the field-lines, resists with its own momentum there where it is perpendicular both to the velocity vector and the magnetic field. This effect is called α -effect. Since the toroidal (azimuthal) field can be easily generated by the poloidal (axial) field during differential rotation, the α -effect allows the conversion of the toroidal field into poloidal, hence closing the cycle of magnetic dynamo.

As it was shown, the α -effect is non-zero only in the case of reflexive asymmetry of the velocity $\mathbf{u}$ -field, where the mean helicity $\langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega} \rangle$ is not zero. For a lucid understanding of the physical essence of the α -effect, let us consider the situation in Fig.(4.3)

The cyclical events of the velocity field $\mathbf{u}$ and $\nabla \times \mathbf{u}$ create a current

Figure 4.3: Model of the α -effect. (a) Incoming flow of particles across a magnetic-field line. (b) This flow "twist" the field line and generates a secondary current, which influences subsequent flows of particles. (c) The process is cyclical, thus generating complicated loop structures [14].

$$I = \int (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{u}) dV \neq 0 \quad (4.9)$$

This event warps and winds the field-lines of the initial field $\mathbf{B}_0$. Each loop is connected with an elementary superficial current and the mean spatial value of these currents will have the form

$$\mathbf{j} = \sigma \alpha \mathbf{B}_0 \quad (4.10)$$

It is evident that the process can be weakened diffusion.

4.4 The effect of $\nabla n \times \nabla T$

When ∇n and ∇T are not parallel, an electromotive force is generated in a plasma that drives the current and produces a magnetic field. This term should be added to the standard

induction equation, which acquires the form

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} - \nabla \times (D_m \nabla \times \mathbf{B}) + \frac{\nabla n \times T}{ne} \quad (4.11)$$

where D_m is the magnetic diffusivity η/μ . The first term on the right-hand side describes the convection of the magnetic field with a plasma flow (line-tying), the second term describes joule dissipation (in the case of a uniform magnetic diffusivity, it reduces to a diffusion term $D_M \nabla^2 \mathbf{B}$, and the last term is the thermo-electromotive force [37].

Chapter 5

Experimental Set-Up and Diagnostics

Diagnostics are motivated from the necessity to know the plasma parameters and their time evolution. Once we have diagnostic experimental data, for example temperature, density, radius, current and so on, we can make analytical inferences out of it, and then we may obtain valuable information about the physical behavior of the self-organized structures. All these can lead to a theoretical understanding of the structural changes of plasmas in space and time. Therefore, in order to understand the complex phenomena within the observed spiral or other plasma structures in dense magnetized plasma, temporal and spatial experimental diagnostics with high resolution are necessary [35, 92–94], whose detailed description is in section 5.3.

5.1 The Device Stand 300

The S-300, a high-current pulsed power generator for investigation of linear implosions in the Kurchatov Institute in Moscow, was used to generate a z-pinch in a series of experiments from 1996 [4, 5]. The generator was designed for the output parameters: voltage 0.7–1.3MV, power 10 TW, current 2-3 MA; the current increase to a maximal value at time $t \sim 100$ ns. During the experiments it was used Al wire of $120 \mu\text{m}$ diameter [3, 95]. The S-300 generator

was constructed on the basis of multi-module principles (eight modules) and consists of capacitive energy storage system, two water stages of pulse forming, water transmission lines and a vacuum chamber with energy concentrator inside it. The output forming stage, the transmission lines and the vacuum chamber were placed in a common water tank. See Fig.(5.1) and Fig.(5.2) in the next pages for upper view of the entire device, a side view of the wire position, and lateral view of the whole S-300 device.

Standt - 300 Plasma Device RCC Kurchatow institute Moscow

Figure 5.1: The S-300. Upper view of the entire device and side view of the wire position.

GENERATOR Stand 300 - Brief Description

Figure 5.2: The S-300. Side view

5.2 PF-1000 Plasma Focus Device

We present in this section an schematic representation of the experimental set-up of the PF-1000 (Fig.(5.3)), since the diagnostic methods are similar to the ones used for the S-300, and because it has also been observed ringed and spiral structures during the pinch phase of those experiments [96].

See also Sec.(6.1) for the specific technical details with which the images used in this work were obtained.

Figure 5.3: PF-1000's experimental set-up in Warsaw

5.3 Plasma Diagnostic Methods Related with this Work

For the gathering of information of plasma generated by these devices we use standard diagnostic techniques [35, 92, 97]. In plasma it is measured the density of particles [35], electrical conductivity, heat conduction, viscosity [98, 99] etc. For such purpose some of the techniques most closely related with this work can be studied below.

5.3.1 Streak Camera

The streak camera has the advantage over framing cameras or image dissecting cameras that it allows continuous time resolution of the order of nanoseconds by abstracting a narrow segment of a fast moving event by means of a rotating mirror or a shifting electric field [35, 100].

For the case of the shifting electric field, the principle is as follows [35, 100, 101]: the photons emitted by the z-pinch discharge are focused by a lens toward the streak camera slit and then they go to a detector where electrons are liberated. An electric field, which grows in time, is on the other side of this surface. The idea of the electric field is to shift the emitted electrons, so that they strike a sensitive film at a different position, corresponding to the time evolution of the z-pinch. Once we have obtained a picture, for example in wire discharge experiments we can measure the time evolution of the corona diameter, and even its expansion velocity by using (for example) the finite difference scheme

$$v = \frac{r_{i+1} - r_i}{t_{i+1} - t_i} \quad (5.1)$$

where $r_{i+1} - r_i$ is the measured differences in the radii in the streak camera record and $t_{i+1} - t_i$ represents the time interval between measured radii.

5.3.2 Rogowski Belt for Current Measurement

Since the electrical current in most plasma physics experiments is both large and rapidly varying, it is convenient to take advantage of the resulting rapidly varying magnetic induction in devising methods of measuring the current. A pickup coil arrangement which permits the determination of the current under circumstances where the geometry is not so precisely known is the widely used Rogowski coil or belt. A Rogowski coil is essentially a multiturn solenoid deformed into a torus which encircles the current to be measured [97]. For current measurements it is necessary the absolute calibration of the Rogowski coil. A sketch of such a torus, together with an RC integrating network, is shown in Fig.(5.4).

The flux at any time is related to the main current I , the source of the magnetic induction,

Figure 5.4: Rogowski coil, with passive integration network [97]

by an equation of the form

$$\phi(t) = K n I(t) \quad (5.2)$$

where n is the total number of turns on the pickup coil and K is a proportionality constant which depends on the geometry of the coil and the current distribution. The equation for the output voltage then becomes

$$V(t) = \frac{K n}{R C} I(t) \quad (5.3)$$

with R and C the resistance and capacitance of the integrating network. Ampere's law can be applied to a closed path which threads the turns of the winding Rogowski coil in such a manner that each element of path length is essentially perpendicular to the plane of the turn it threads. If the turns are evenly spaced, the result can be written

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \iint_s \mathbf{i} \cdot d\mathbf{s} \\ &= \frac{1}{\mu_0} \oiint \nabla \times \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{s} \\ &= \frac{1}{\mu_0} \oint \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{l} = \frac{S}{\mu_0 n} \oint \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{n}, \end{aligned} \quad (5.4)$$

where S is the effective length of the deformed solenoid (the mean circumference of the torus), $d\mathbf{n}$ is a vector in the direction of $d\mathbf{l}$ but with magnitude ndl/S and n is the total number of turns. If the individual turns have constant cross-sectional area A , we may write 5.4 in the form

$$I = \frac{S}{\mu_0 n A} \int A \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{n} = \frac{S}{\mu_0 n A} \int d\phi = \frac{S\phi}{\mu_0 n A} \quad (5.5)$$

where ϕ is the total flux threading the turns of the Rogowski coil.

In Eq. 5.5 the variation of the magnetic induction over the area of an individual turn has been assumed negligible, Except for the error (usually very small) introduced by this assumption, the equation shows that the constant K in Eqs. 5.2 and 5.3 is given by the easily evaluated relation

$$K = \frac{\mu_0 A}{S}, \quad (5.6)$$

and is independent of the manner in which the main current threads the opening of the torus. It is this feature which accounts for the wide use of Rogowski coils, since it permits great flexibility in positioning the coil with respect to the current to be measured. The result is also independent of the details of the major shape of the cross section of each turn, provided only that the coil has a shape topologically equivalent to a torus. From Eq. ??

$$V = \frac{R}{n} I \quad (5.7)$$

it is evident that the output voltage gives a direct measure of the main current and the Rogowski coil acts simply as a current transformer.

In many plasma physics experiments there may be large amounts of $d\phi/dt$ passing through the major opening of the torus as a result of currents other than the one being measured. Current measurements with a Rogowski coil like that shown in Fig.(5.4) may be

seriously in error in such cases, because of the large area of the individual turns. A common and useful way of virtually eliminating this source of error is to bring the end of the coil winding wire back through the turns of the coil to the initial end, as shown in Fig.(5.5), so that flux which threads the major opening of the torus no longer threads any portion of the measuring circuit [97].

Figure 5.5: Rogowski coil wound to minimize the effect of flux threading through major opening [97]

5.3.3 Determination of B_ϕ

Once we have the variation of the pinch diameter from the streak camera record, we can use as well the current measured with a Rogowski coil (see section 5.3.2), and assuming that all the current is inside the observed object, we can use the formula for calculation of the magnetic field in a long straight wire (Eq.(4.3)). But now instead of a wire of negligible thickness, we have a cylinder of finite diameter, therefore we have a *current differential*, and we would like to calculate the average magnetic field inside that cylinder to obtain $\bar{B}_\phi$. The average value of the magnetic field inside the corona is defined as:

$$\bar{B} = \frac{1}{S} \iint B dS$$

where S is the total area from which we are calculating the average magnetic field.

We begin the evaluation of this formula by considering

$$dB_\varphi = \frac{\mu_0 dI_z}{2\pi\rho}$$

where ρ is the differential radius. Let us define the current density as

$$\mathbf{j} = \frac{I}{\pi R^2}$$

and suppose that $\mathbf{j}$ depends on the differential radius as

$$I_\varphi = \mathbf{j} \cdot \pi \rho$$

Therefore

$$B_\varphi(\rho) = \frac{\mu_0(\mathbf{j} \pi \rho^2)}{2\pi\rho} = \frac{\mu_0 \mathbf{j} \rho}{2}$$

We need to integrate

$$\bar{B}_\varphi = \frac{1}{\rho} \int_0^R \mathbf{B} dS$$

where $S = \pi R^2$, $dS = 2\pi\rho d\rho$ and $B_\varphi(\rho) = \mu_0 \mathbf{j} \rho/2$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{B}_\varphi(\rho) &= \frac{1}{\pi R^2} \int_0^R \left(\frac{\mu_0 \mathbf{j} \rho}{2} \right) \cdot (2\pi\rho d\rho) \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{\pi R^2} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_0 \mathbf{j}}{2} \right) \cdot (2\pi) \int_0^R \rho \cdot \rho d\rho \\ &= \frac{\mu_0 \mathbf{j}}{R^2} \int_0^R \rho^2 d\rho \\ &= \frac{\mu_0 \mathbf{j}}{R^2} \cdot \frac{R^3}{3} \\ &= \frac{\mu_0 \mathbf{j} R}{3} \end{aligned}$$

(5.8)

but $\mathbf{j} = I_z/\pi R^2$ on the boundary, therefore

$$\bar{B}_\varphi = \frac{\mu_0 \left(\frac{I_z}{\pi R^2} \right) R}{3} = \frac{\mu_0 I_z R}{3\pi R^2},$$

from which we finally can obtain

$$\bar{B}_\varphi = \frac{\mu_0 I_z}{3\pi R} \quad (5.9)$$

or, as it was used for the calculations in this work

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{B}_\varphi[\text{T}] &= \frac{4\pi 10^{-7} [\text{T} \cdot \text{m}/\text{A}] \cdot I_z[\text{A}]}{3\pi R[\text{m}]} \\ &= \frac{4}{3} 10^{-7} [\text{T} \cdot \text{m}/\text{A}] \cdot \frac{I_z[\text{A}]}{R[\text{m}]} \end{aligned} \quad (5.10)$$

We have come to the result that the average magnetic field is similar to the magnetic field at the boundary, modulo a constant.

We can also calculate the magnetic pressure, once we have $\bar{B}_\phi$:

$$p = \frac{\bar{B}_\phi^2}{2\mu_0} \quad (5.11)$$

and of course we may attempt to seek an equality between the magnetic pressure and the thermodynamic pressure, to obtain the temperature in Kelvins:

$$n_e kT = \frac{\bar{B}_\phi^2}{2\mu_0} \quad (5.12)$$

5.3.4 PIN Diode

The PIN diodes are semiconductor diodes mostly made of a silicon [102], meant for detection of photons in visible and X-ray range [35]. The diode is connected to a voltage of 50-70 V in a closed sense and the falling photons liberate electrons in the diode, which can be registered in the form of a current in the diode in a oscilloscope (Fig.(5.6))

Figure 5.6: Scheme of the PIN diode, showing some common parameters. In particular it is shown an Al foil to screen out radiation in the visible region.

We must know the efficiency of the PIN diode, which for the pulsed experiments described in this work is about 0.27 A/W.

Since we know the applied potential difference and the resistance, we can deduce the current produced by the incoming electrons:

$$\frac{V}{R} = I$$

and because we know that

$$I = \frac{dQ}{dt}$$

we may write

$$\int \frac{V}{R} dt = \int dQ$$

and the result can be multiplied by a factor of $4\pi r^2$ where r is the distance from the actual position of the plasma to the emplacement of the PIN diode, thus obtaining the

total energy emitted, within the angle 4π , by the plasma, assuming that the radiation is isotropic. Moreover, since we can put a thin Al foil to screen out optical radiation, we may detect energy in the region 20-70 eV. If we convert eV to J, it would mean that we can measure energy in the region $3.204 \times 10^{-18} \text{J} \leq \text{Energy} \leq 1.1214 \times 10^{-17} \text{J}$ but we know that the photons emitted by the pinched plasma fall into the PIN diode with an energy $h\nu$ where h is the Planck constant and ν is the frequency of the photons. Since we know the total energy, and from other methods we may calculate the wavelength of the radiation then we can calculate the total number of photons [35, 103].

5.3.5 Time Integrated Pinhole (Obscure) Camera

During the destruction of the pinch we encounter small submillimetric zones which intensely radiate X-rays, so called hot spots. For picturing these localities with short life range it is used the pinhole camera [35, 104] (Fig.(5.7)). The source of radiation is pictured through a hole with a diameter between $50 - 100 \mu\text{m}$ and a film or a CCD chip. The enlargement of the picture is given by the ratio a/b , where a is the distance from the plasma to the hole of the camera, b is the distance from the hole to the film. The fuzziness of the picture Δy is given by the diameter Φ of the little hole and the geometry of the image formation

$$\Delta y = \Phi \frac{a+b}{a},$$

The estimation of the energy of photons can be done by absolutely calibrated filters on which the energy is $E = h\nu_i n_i$ where ν_i is the i^{th} frequency and n_i is the number of photons corresponding to the i^{th} frequency. By using different filters we can stop radiation with frequencies lower than certain absorption threshold. Frequently it is used a pinhole camera with 2 or 3 apertures, each one with a different filter [35, 105–107].

Time integrated means that the image is formed from a collected radiation within a

Figure 5.7: Scheme of the pinhole camera. See text above for explanation of literals

set-up interval of time.

5.3.6 XUV and Visible Frame Cameras

The densely magnetized, cold plasmas that we mention in this work have been photographed using standard optical techniques [35, 108]. From one discharge it was obtained 2-3 frames with 1 ns exposure and 10-20 ns of time delay (with respect to the start of the discharge).

5.3.7 Schlieren Method

The Schlieren method [35, 109] is useful for visualizing big gradients of plasma electrons in the perpendicular sense to the diagnosed beam. The principle of the method resides on the refraction of the electro-magnetic waves. This is schematically depicted in figure 5.8. The Schlieren technique in plasma physics often uses a laser beam [110]

From Fig.(5.8) it is clear that we have in the projected image measurable differences at length Δy (the distance from the center of the little screen towards the boundary of the non-parallel beams) and width Δl (the width of the plasma), and an angle α between the parallel beams and the deviated beams. From these data we can infer approximately the concentration of electrons at each Δl , Δy step from the formula:

$$\Delta n_e \geq \frac{\alpha \Delta y}{4.5 \times 10^{-16} \lambda \Delta l}, \quad (5.13)$$

Figure 5.8: A schematic representation of the Schlieren method. It can be seen that non-parallel beams go around the little screen, and from the gradient of intensities and the angle from the parallel beams, we may infer the gradient of concentrations. See text below for explanation of literals

where λ is the wavelength of the laser beam [35].

The resulting image renders a qualitative idea of the gradients of concentration, as we may appreciate in figure 5.9.

Figure 5.9: Schlieren photograph of one of the observed spirals

5.3.8 Wollanstone Prism

A special type of differential interferometer is the Wollanstone prism [35]. It is used mostly in combination with a system of two symmetrical, Schlieren prisms and a laser like a source of radiation. During the usage of the polarizator, which substitutes sharp Schlieren diagnostics, the system is relatively simple a insensible to vibrations and does not demand expensive optics. It is useful for measuring high electron densities $n_e > 10^{25}\text{m}^{-3}$, high

gradients of densities and for Faraday rotation of the polarization plane of the magnetic field. The prism is composed of 2 ceramic wedges with mutually perpendicular optical axes against the sense of the trajectory of the beam (Fig.(5.10)):

Figure 5.10: Schematic representation of the trajectory of the beam into the Wollaston prism.

The polarized light falls into the prism under an angle of 45° with respect to the optical axis and during the falling fissions itself into ordinary and extraordinary beams with a mutually perpendicular polarization running in the same direction and with different speed. In the second prism the roles of ordinary and extraordinary are reversed to each other. During the exit from the prism both beams are mutually deviated by an angle

$$\epsilon = 2(N_e - N_o) \tan(\alpha)$$

The outgoing beams have orthogonal polarization and it is possible to pack them again with another polarizator rotated 45° and thus find the components, which can in turn interfere. The Wollaston prism can be used even with a bunch of beams, which are not parallel. Both outgoing bunches from the prism have a mutual difference of phases proportional to the distance h from the middle of the plane and they create interference strips parallel with the biggest angle of mutual distance.

$$h_0 = \frac{\lambda}{\epsilon} = \frac{\lambda}{2\Delta n \tan \alpha}$$

The distance between bunches (0.5 mm for $\alpha = 3^\circ$) imposes a demand on the size of the image from the source of light, which for a good contrast should be smaller than $h_0/4$. For weakening it is used only 20% of light. It is possible to see schematically how does it works the Wollanstone prism (Fig.(5.11)).

Figure 5.11: A schematic representation of the trajectories of beams with the Wollanstone prism, marked in the figure with a capital "W". From this result the so-called differential interferometry.

The object plane **O** is imaged with the lens *L* into the screen *S*. The Wollanstone prism *W* and the polarizator *P* are emplaced at the focus plane *F*. The polarization of the beams is 45° against the plane of the image. The distance between bunches h_0 in the plane of the Wollanstone prism is related with the distances between bunches η in the object plane

$$\eta = \frac{f}{w} h_0 = \frac{f \lambda}{w \varepsilon}$$

In the little screen the distance between bunches is

$$E = \frac{v - f}{w} h_0 = \frac{v - f}{w} \frac{\lambda}{h}$$

From the shown relations it comes that with a change in w (done by a change in the positions of the Wollanstone prisms) it is possible to change the dispersion of the bunches from ∞ to a very small point. The rotated field from the bunches can be done by rotating the Wollanstone prism together with the polarization of the falling beams and the polarizator.

From (D7) it is clear that, shall we have two points P'_1 and P'_2 , they would correspond to the two samples P_1 and P_2 distanced in the object plane about Δy (resolution power): according to

$$\frac{\Delta y}{f} = \frac{E}{v - f} = \frac{\varepsilon(v - f - w)}{v - f}$$

it is valid that:

$$\Delta y = \varepsilon(v - f - w) \frac{u}{v}.$$

Δy can be in the tenths of mm. Thus the differential interferometer measures the differences in the change of the optical trajectories of two tested beams going through the tested object with two small separations y -values and measures the gradient $\Delta n / \Delta y$ projected as fringes. From that the method is sometimes called gradient interferometer. Small local shifts of the interferenced beams is because of quality defects in the Schlieren lens and in the diagnostics window in comparison with the remaining types of interferometry [35].

5.3.9 Spectroscopy

When mixed electro-magnetic radiation, emitted by atoms involved in transition energy processes, passes through a prism or a gritted crystal inside a device called spectrometer, it separates into its individual components, often identifiable as individual lines into photographic film, or as distributions of peaks with varying amplitudes and heights [8]. The heights of these peaks (intensities) and their broadening can give information about electron (or ion) concentrations and temperature [111, 112]. The pattern of lines in the photographic films can also give valuable information about the type of atoms, their temperature and even concentration for a given plasma experiment [113]. An illustration of such pattern of lines corresponding to different radiation ranges for hydrogen is given in Fig.(5.12)

Figure 5.12: Scheme of the hydrogen energy levels [8]

The Local Thermal Equilibrium (LTE) Model

In the LTE model it is assumed that the distribution of population densities of the electrons is determined exclusively by particle collision processes and that the latter take place with sufficient rapidity that the distribution responds instantaneously to any change in the plasma conditions. In such circumstances each process is accompanied by its inverse and these pairs of processes occur at equal rates by the principle of detailed balance. Thus the distribution of population densities of the energy levels of the electrons is the same as it would be in a system in complete thermodynamic equilibrium. The population distribution is determined by the statistical mechanical law of equipartition among energy levels and does not require knowledge of atomic cross sections for its calculation. Thus, although the plasma temperature and density may vary in space and time, the distribution of population densities at any instant and point in space depends entirely on local values of temperature, density, and chemical composition of the plasma. The uncertainty in predictions of spec-

tral line intensities from a LTE model plasma depend on the uncertainties in the values of these plasma parameters and of the atomic transition probabilities [112]. The model LTE is applied in the case that electron collisions dominate [35].

If the free electrons are distributed among the energy levels available to them, according to statistical mechanics, their velocities have a Maxwellian distribution. Thus the number of electrons with velocities v and $v + dv$ is [112]

$$dn_v = n_e 4\pi \left(\frac{m}{2kT_e} \right)^{3/2} \cdot \exp \left(\frac{-mv^2}{2kT_e} \right) v^2 dv \quad (5.14)$$

LTE was also the basis for the development of Saha's equation.

The Saha Equation

The Indian physicists Saha, using Nernst's theorem, derived from classical thermodynamics [114] an expression which tells the ratio of number of particles of two consecutive ionization stages [105].

Quantum statistical mechanics shows that in thermal equilibrium the population of any two (single) quantum states of a system are related by the Boltzmann factor

$$N_i/N_j = \exp[-(E_i - E_j)/T]$$

Now when both i and j are bound states of the atom, no complications enter. However, if the state j (say) consists of a state in which the atom is ionized and thus the electron is free, a more careful enumeration of the quantum states is necessary in order to specify not just the distribution of states within the specific ionization state of the atom, but also the distribution among the various different possible ionization states of an atomic species (singly and multiply ionized).

Just as before, we must recognize the degeneracy of the states i and j . This arises first because of the statistical weights g_i , g_j , but secondly, in the case of ionization, because of

the number of possible states of the free electron. The states are enumerated quite readily as follows.

Consider an assembly of electrons and atoms within a volume V . Specifically suppose that there are a total of N_i atoms in the specific level of ionization stage i , N_{i+1} in a specific level of ionization stage $i + 1$, and N_e electrons in the volume. We know that in thermal equilibrium the ratio of the probability of finding the system in this state to the probability of finding it in a state with exactly one further ionization (i.e., $N_i \rightarrow N_i - 1, N_{i+1} \rightarrow N_{i+1} + 1, N_e \rightarrow N_e + 1$), in which the electron liberated has speed v , is $\exp[-(\xi_i + \frac{1}{2}mv^2)/T]$ times the ratio of the number of possible quantum states for each case (ξ_i is the energy difference between states i and $i + 1$, the ionization energy). The ratio of the number of possible distinguishable arrangements of $K + 1$ electrons among L states to that of K electrons L states is $(L - K)/(K + 1) \approx L/K$ (for $L \gg K \gg 1$), the factor $1/(K + 1)$ arising because individual electrons are indistinguishable .

For a free electron the number of possible quantum states is

$$L = 2 \frac{V}{(2\pi)^3} 4\pi k^2 dk = 2 \frac{V}{(2\pi)^3} 4\pi \frac{m^3}{\hbar^3} v^2 dv,$$

where $2V/(2\pi)^3$ is the density of states in k space (allowing for two possible spin states) and $k = mv/\hbar$ is the de Broglie wave number of the electron. Also, the number of electrons in our velocity interval of interest is, from the Maxwellian distribution,

$$K = \left(\frac{m}{2\pi T} \right)^{3/2} N_e e^{-mv^2/2T} \cdot 4\pi v^2 dv.$$

Substituting these values we find the ratio of the number of free electron states to be

$$\frac{L}{K} = 2 \frac{V}{N_e} \frac{m^3}{h^3} \frac{2\pi T}{m} e^{mv^2/2T}.$$

The translational states of the atom before and after ionization are approximately equal because the mass change is very small; therefore, the ratio of the number of indistinguishable ion states is

$$\frac{g_{i+1}L_{i+1}}{N_{i+1}} \left(\frac{g_iL_i}{N_i} \right)^{-1} = \frac{g_{i+1}N_i}{g_iN_{i+1}},$$

where $L_i \approx L_{i+1}$ is the number of translational states for a single ion. Hence, the total ratio of the number of states of the system is

$$\frac{N_i g_{i+1}}{N_{i+1} g_i} \frac{2V}{N_e} \frac{m^3}{h^3} \frac{2\pi T^{3/2}}{m} e^{mv^2/2T}.$$

Now we multiply this by $\exp(-\xi_i - \frac{1}{2}mv^2)/T$ in order to obtain the ratio of the probabilities of the configurations and set this ratio equal to 1, since thermal equilibrium corresponds to the most probable state. Then we find

$$\frac{n_e n_{i+1}}{n_i} = \frac{g_{i+1}}{g_i} \left[\frac{2m^3}{h^3} \left(\frac{2\pi T}{m} \right)^{3/2} \right] e^{-\xi_i/T} \quad (5.15)$$

where n refers to the number density (N/V) of a species.

This equation is a form of what is called the Saha equation and determines the relative populations of the ionization states in thermal equilibrium. The term in square brackets is roughly equal to the inverse of the volume of a cube of side length equal to the thermal de Broglie electron wavelength. It is usually much bigger than n_e , that is, there is on average much less than one electron in a de Broglie cube. One thus finds that the exponent, ξ_i/T , can be appreciable but still allow a high degree of ionization (n_{i+1}/n_i) [92].

There are several version of the Saha equation [19, 27, 35, 112, 114] All of them are relations which permit the estimation of the concentration of particles from spectroscopy. The one which in particular we used for this work was [27]

$$\frac{n_{z+1}}{n_z} n_e = \frac{\sigma_{z+1}}{\sigma_z} \cdot 6 \times 10^{27} (kT_{[eV]})^{3/2} \cdot e^{\frac{E_i}{kT_{[eV]}}} \quad (5.16)$$

and n_{z+1}/n_z should be ~ 1 .

Line Broadening

- *Natural Line Broadening*

This arises because of the fact that the quantum states of an atom do not have a single energy, but a small spread in energy. The energy spread arises because perturbations of the atomic system due to interaction with the electro-magnetic fields of virtual (or real) photons cause the quantum states to be only approximate eigenmodes of the system. The effective spread in energy of a quantum state is given by the uncertainty principle

$$\Delta E \approx h/2\pi\tau$$

where the lifetime τ is given by

$$\frac{2}{\tau} = \sum_j A_{ij},$$

the sum of all possible spontaneous transitions (with a factor 2 for providing a standard form of the line profile).

The corresponding line broadening of the spectral lines of transitions from this broadened state i , due to the broadening of only this state, is simply

$$\Delta\nu = \Delta E/h \approx 1/2\pi\tau.$$

The shape of the broadened lines is determined by the shape of the energy broadening. This may be shown to be the Fourier transform of the square root of the exponentially decaying probability of the atom being in the i^{th} state. The resulting spectral shape is

$$I(\nu) = I(\nu_0) \frac{1}{1 + [(\nu - \nu_0)2\pi\tau]^2}$$

where I is the intensity and ν_0 the line center (note that if the lower level k is also broadened, for example, when it is not the ground state, the value to be used for $2/\tau$ is $\sum A_{ij} + \sum A_{kj}$).

It is common to use as a measure of the line width (regardless of the precise line shape) the full width at half maximum (FWHM). This is illustrated for a Lorentzian line shape in Fig.(6.18). Its relationship to the lifetime is

$$\Delta\nu_{1/2} = 1/\pi\tau.$$

Figure 5.13: The Lorentzian line shape typical of natural broadening: $I(\nu) = (1 + \Delta\nu^2)^{-1}$, with $\Delta\nu$ in units of $1/2\pi\tau$. The Full Width at half maximum is shown FWHM [92].

Because $A_{ij} \propto V_{ij}^3$, natural broadening, though usually negligible in the visible range, can become important for the extreme ultraviolet lines of highly ionized impurities [92].

- *Doppler Broadening*

This arises straightforwardly from the Doppler shift caused by thermal particle motion

$$\Delta\nu = \nu - \nu_0 = \nu_0 v/c,$$

where v is the particle velocity in the line of sight. For an atom velocity distribution $f(v)$, this gives a line shape

$$I(\nu) \propto f([\nu/\nu_0 - 1]c),$$

A Maxwellian velocity distribution gives rise to a Gaussian line profile

$$I(\nu) = I(\nu_0) \exp[-(\nu - \nu_0)^2 c^2 / 2v_{ta}^2 \nu_0^2],$$

where $v_{ta}^2 = T_a/m_a$, the subscript a referring to the emitting atom. The FWHM is

$$\Delta\nu_{1/2} = \nu_0(v_{ta}/c)(2 \ln 2)^{1/2}$$

Of course, widths can also be expressed in terms of wavelengths λ . For small widths $\Delta\lambda/\lambda = \Delta\nu/\nu$ [92].

- *Pressure Broadening*

This effect is also variously called collisional broadening or Stark broadening and arises from the influence of nearby particles upon the emitting atom. There are two main approaches to calculating the broadening, starting from opposite extremes: The impact or quasistatic approximations are applicable according as $\Delta\nu \ll t_p^{-1}$ or $\Delta\nu \gg t_p^{-1}$, where t_p is the duration of the perturbing interaction. Because of the difference in electron and ion velocities, the electron effects are usually best approximated by the impact approach while ion perturbations, for most of the line, are best modeled using the quasistatic approximation. It turns out too that the ion effects dominate the line width, at least for hydrogen lines. Knowing the Stark effect on the line, we then must calculate the statistical distribution of electric field experienced by the atoms. For the case of ions as perturbers in a plasma, provided the atom is significantly closer to one ion than all the others, the electrical field E in the vicinity of that ion is $E \propto 1/r^2$, where r is the distance from that nearest ion. Also the proportion of space in that vicinity corresponding to r and hence the probability of experiencing E , say $P(E)dE$, is proportional to the volume of the spherical shell $4\pi r^2 dr$. Therefore, the distribution of intensity in the line is

$$I(\nu)d\nu \propto P(E)dE \propto -r^2 dr.$$

Now $E \propto 1/r^2$ so $-r^2 dr \propto E^{-5/2} dE$; also $\Delta\nu \propto E$ and hence,

$$I(\nu)d\nu \propto E^{-5/2} dE \propto (\Delta\nu)^{-5/2} d\nu.$$

Thus the shape of the line in the region where E and hence $\Delta\nu$ is large is $I(\nu) \propto (\Delta\nu)^{-5/2}$.

This functional distribution holds only up to a radius such that the electric field contributions from other ions are of the same order as that of the initial ion. This will occur when $\frac{4}{3}\pi r^3 \approx 1/n_i$ at $\Delta\nu \propto E \propto n_i^{2/3}$. At this point some kind of cutoff must be applied to $P(E)$, since obviously the relevant volume does not continue to increase. Thus the width of the line will be proportional to this cutoff, that is, to $n_i^{2/3}$. Although this simple approach (often called the nearest neighbor treatment) does not give a full picture of the complexity of the problem nor account for important corrections due to electron effects (especially near $\Delta\nu = 0$), it does quite accurately give the density dependence of the line width [92].

- *Combinations of Broadening Effects*

Sometimes both Doppler and other broadening effects and also, possibly, the finite resolution of the measuring instrument, are important. In general, when such a situation occurs, if there are two independent profiles, say $f_1(\Delta\nu)$ and $f_2(\Delta\nu)$, then the resulting observed profile is the convolution of the two profile functions:

$$f(\Delta\nu) = \int f_1(\Delta\nu - \Delta\nu') f_2(\Delta\nu') d(\Delta\nu').$$

Similarly, for further broadening functions f_3 , and so forth, further convolutions are formed [92].

- *Reabsorption: Optically Thick Lines*

We may regard the primary effect of reabsorption as being to place a "ceiling" at the blackbody level on the maximum radiation intensity.

Incidentally, this provides a simple way to check whether reabsorption is important. Calculate the intensity under the assumption that reabsorption is negligible by integrating the emissivity along the line of sight. If this is significantly less than the appropriate blackbody level, then reabsorption may indeed be ignored.

Spectrometer Based on Measurement of Absorption of Radiation During Reflection

Absorption of falling X-ray radiation from the surface of materials is angle-dependent and can be substantially changed for small angles of about some arc-steps. The change in absorption and reflectivity is for a certain wavelength dependent on the angle of falling and approximately can be taken as a rule, that the absorption of mono-energetic radiation wave λ occurs during angles of falling bigger than an angle α with arc-step comparable in size with the wavelength of the wave in nm:

$$\alpha[^\circ] \approx \lambda[\text{nm.}] \quad (5.17)$$

The angle α is the angle between the reflective surface and the falling beam. For example, for a radiation with wavelength of 20 nm, absorption occurs for angles $> 20^\circ$, and is reflected for angles $< 20^\circ$. Therefore, if the device is set-up with an angle of 20° , any radiation with a wavelength > 20 nm will be reflected, and radiations < 20 nm are absorbed. The speed of decreasing depends on the quality of roughness of the surface on reflection. For a rough surface it is valid the same conditions as in optical radiation, for it should be smaller than 1/10 of the wavelength, and hence in nm. For example, in Fig.(5.14) it is shown the dependency of intensity of reflected Balmer lines of Hydrogen-like carbon CVI 18.22 nm to the falling angle, if the reflecting surface is ceramic with a roughness of 1 nm. this kind of roughness cannot be achieved mechanically and for that purpose it is used crystal surfaces [35].

The mechanical construction of spectrometer makes possible the step-wise measuring of the intensity for different angles of reflection. For detection it is used a PIN diode and this method has time resolving capability. An scheme of the spectrometer is shown in Fig.(5.15) [35].

Figure 5.14: Dependency of reflectivity of 18.22nm with the angle of falling [35].

Figure 5.15: Scheme of a spectrometer based on glancing angle [35].

Part II

**Experimental Results and their
Evaluation**

Chapter 6

Description of Experimental Records

6.1 XUV and Visible Frame Camera

Helical structures have been clearly identified in the visible region with visible frame camera, and regular ring structures in the soft x-ray region with XUV-frame camera, during z-pinch discharges. The images were obtained as follows [115]:

- *Visible image* Three frame image converter cameras (grabbing the plasma images from the radial direction with an exposure time of 1 ns and a delay of 10-15 ns).
- *XUV image* Photography in the soft X-ray region based on frame image converter cameras equipped with three semiconductor detectors.

Besides it was also used a pinhole camera, 100 μm diameter pinhole filtered by mylar and Al foils, located in the radial position for detection of hot spots, but only a small percentage of the overall emission corresponds to unstable and randomly located hot spots that emit the non-thermal radiation at the keV range.

The spiral structures are composed of two interwoven tubes, and together they have dimensions $\approx 8\text{mm}$ long and $\approx 2\text{mm}$ diameter. The XUV-ray regular forms have dimensions $\approx 8\text{mm}$ long and $\approx 2\text{mm}$ diameter in the rings (or necks, as we shall be using both terms indistinctly from now on) as can be seen in Fig.(6.1). The spirals are located inside the

ringed hotter plasma structure. A schematic representation of this described situation can be seen in Fig.(6.2). The helical structures make one and a half turn lengthwise. The rings of the regular structures have a distance between them $d \approx 1\text{mm}$. The type of instability is $m=1$.

Figure 6.1: Shot (19.2), time 50 ns: A) Visible frame: spiral-like surface of dense magnetized plasma. B) XUV frame: plasma rings on the surface of the plasma corona (soft X-ray).

Figure 6.2: A schematic model for the physical positions of the helical and ringed self-organized structures. The program Mathematica© drew the elements of the scheme as follows (mind the fact that Mathematica has a special syntax). The "nodes" were drawn with the function: `PointParametricPlot3D[{(3+Cos[u])Cos[v], (3+Cos[u])Sin[v], Sin[u]}, {u, -Pi/2, Pi/2}, {v, 0, 2Pi}, Boxed->False, PlotPoints->{25, 50}, ViewPoint->{1, 5, 1}]`. The "necks" or "rings" were obtained (after some erasing of the external points) by: `PointParametricPlot3D[{(3+Cos[u])Cos[v], (3+Cos[u])Sin[v], Sin[u]}, {u, 0, 2Pi}, {v, 0, 2Pi}, Boxed->False, PlotPoints->{25, 50}, ViewPoint->{1, 5, 1}]`. And for the helicoidal tube: `ParametricPlot3D[{Sin[u]+Cos[t], Cos[u]+Sin[t], u}, {t, 0, 2Pi}, {u, 0, 15}, PlotPoints->{35, 35}, Boxed->False, Axes->False]`.

Notice that in Fig.(6.2) it is also indicated the thickness of the plasma layer forming the necks and nodes. Moreover, we also point the attention that particles are constantly expelled from the nodes and radiation is emitted from the necks [27].

6.2 Streak Camera

The variation in time of the discharge was possible with visible photography with streak camera, observing the plasma from the radial direction with the slit aligned perpendicular to the wire axis [115].

6.2.1 Measurement of Variation of Radius over Time

Out of two streak camera shots, numbered 99.05.17.1 and 99.05.19.2 from the Stand-300 device (from now on, only referred as "shot 17.1 and 19.2"), it was measured directly the variations of the radius of the neck (inner radius) and node (outer radius) with respect to time, and the data of the radii was smoothed with the sliding window technique, whose program (in BASIC) is as follows:

```

FOR  $i = 1$  TO  $last$ 
  FOR  $j = 1$  TO 4
    IF NOT ( $i + j > last$ ) THEN
       $radius(i) = radius(i) + last(i + j)$ 
    END IF
  NEXT  $j$ 
   $radius(i) = radius(i)/5$ 
NEXT  $i$ 

```

The result of it is depicted in Fig.(6.3).

6.2.2 Velocity Variation over Time

From the smoothed radii data it was obtained the dependency of variation of velocity with respect to time, for the node and neck using Eq. (5.1). From which we obtained the

Figure 6.3: Dependence of radius with respect to time: (a) From the shot 17.1. (b) From the shot 19.2

Fig.(6.4)

6.2.3 Radius and Velocity at Pinch Phase

For the shot 17.1 (see Fig.(6.5)), the time range of the streak camera was from about 20 ns to 220 ns, with a total of almost 200 ns (the time is measured from the point of the onset of the current). As it may be seen in Fig.(6.3) and Fig.(6.4), in the moment of x-pulse emission at 100 ns the corona had these parameters: The radius was 1 mm (neck) and 2.1×10^{-3} m (node). The typical value of the increase of the corona diameter is about $1 \times 10^4 \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, which we will see is about one order of magnitude less than our results for the velocity of explosions. At 100 ns was attained a maximum velocity of about $10 \times 10^4 \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (neck) and $8 \times 10^4 \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (node) [116].

For the shot 19.2 (see Fig.(6.6)), the time range of the streak camera exposition was from 30 ns to 230 ns, again about 200 ns in total. The radius at 100 ns was 1 mm (neck) and 2.18 (node). At 100 ns was attained a maximum velocity of $6 \times 10^4 \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (neck) and

Figure 6.4: Dependence of velocity of expansion with respect to time. (a) Shot 17.1. (b) Shot 19.2

$4 \times 10^4 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (node) [116].

The coloration shown in Fig.(6.5) and Fig.(6.6) is related with differences of intensity of light on the original record (see the compendium of records on Fig.(6.8) and Fig.(6.9)).

6.2.4 Volume of Ringed Structures

The variation of volume over time of the ringed structures could be estimated as well, using the knowledge of the dependence of the radius over time as follows:

$$Volume = 2 \times l \times \pi \times r \times dx \quad (6.1)$$

where l is the length (8 mm), assumed constant. The variation of the radius r over time was obtained from the streak camera record as shown in Fig.(6.3). Finally we have assumed that the X-ray ringed structure has a thickness of $100 \mu\text{m}$, so small as to be considered a differential of the thickness dx (assumed constant). The results are presented in Fig.(6.7).

Figure 6.5: Shot 17.1. Streak camera record with false coloration done by computer.

Figure 6.6: Shot 19.2. Streak camera record with false coloration done by computer.

Figure 6.7: Variation of volume over time of the ringed structures. (a) shot 17.1. (b) shot 19.2

6.3 Oscilloscope Readings

An oscilloscope record was taken during the shots and provided the data for the current [116].

For the shot 17.1., the maximal current was 2 MA at 250 ns. For the shot 19.2, the maximal current was 1.9 MA around 260 ns. In the moment of x-pulse emission at 100 ns the corona reached a current of ≈ 0.8 MA (shot 17.1) and ≈ 0.94 MA (shot 19.2). The evolution of the current (first channel, the uppermost oscillogram curve) can be observed in Fig.(6.8) and Fig.(6.9). The oscillogram shows as well the temporal position of some of the observed visible and XUV structures, with respect to the time-evolution of the current.

From the oscilloscope readings it was measured a finite amount of data for elaborating graphics about the temporal evolution of the current, which was used in subsequent calculations. This graphics are shown in Fig.(6.10).

Moskva 99
Stand 300,0.8MA
Al 100 μ m
Shot 99.05.17.01

Oscillogram: trace 1- current, trace 2- radial PIN, trace 3 - axial PIN, trace 4 - laser 1

Figure 6.8: Shot 17.1: Compendium of observations for this shot, among them, the oscillogram showing the evolution of the current (first channel, the uppermost oscillogram curve).

Moscow 99
Stand 300,1MA
Al 100 μ m
Shot 99.05.19.02

Oscillogram: trace 1 - current, traces 2, 3 - radial PIN, trace 4 - schlieren 1

Figure 6.9: Shot 19.2: Compendium of observations for this shot, among them, the oscillogram showing the evolution of the current (first channel, the uppermost oscillogram curve). It is V1 and X1 which are shown as examples of the observed structures in Fig.(6.1)

Figure 6.10: Dependency of the current with time. (a) Shot 17.1. (b) Shot 19.2

6.4 Spectroscopy

The technical details of the detection diagnostics were as follows:

- *S-300 facility* Convex mica crystal X-ray spectrometer with one-dimensional spatial resolution, absolutely calibrated in the photon energy interval of 1-10 keV.
- *PF-1000 facility* Time integrated emission spectra of highly charged Al-ions were registered using a focusing spherical mica spectrometer with two-dimensional spatial resolution (FSSR-2D) placed radially to the Al wire. The orientation of the dispersive element of the spectrometer (mica crystal) was such as to obtain spectra with maximal attainable (in this geometry) spatial resolution along the wire.

6.4.1 Spectrograms

Helical forms have been observed also in spectrographic records. For example, in Fig.(6.11) we can appreciate a spiral shape in the X-ray range (17-35 nm), so it has sufficiently high temperature for emission of Al with $z=12,11$ ionization. In Sec.(6.4.2) it will be seen a discussion about their wavelength determination, together with other parameters.

Figure 6.11: Spectroscopy record taken in Prague in 1998. Some of the spectral lines are spirally shaped [117].

Figure 6.12: Spectroscopy record taken in Prague in 1998. The spirals are found in the wavelength 7-8 $\text{\AA}$.

The fact that in the spectral lines are observed spirals, means that precisely at those wavelengths (7-8 Å, as seen in Fig.(6.12))helical structures appeared.

In the helical structure from S-300 at Moscow, the maximum in Planck curve can be in UV, but most of the emission was in the visible range.

A typical Al spectra obtained in the PF-1000 facility, which also shows some spirals in spectroscopy, can be seen in Fig.(6.13).

Figure 6.13: Typical Al spectra as registered with a crystal spectrometer [96]

6.4.2 Wavelength Determination of Helical Forms

Although this part refers to experiments carried out in a small 500 J energy pinch device in Prague [117–120], the methodology of some diagnostic methods is similar, and some of the observations seem to alike to those of the S-300 device, as we will see. The helical structures of Fig.(6.11) and Fig.(6.12) originated from a device localized in Prague. There the temperature was 10 eV, which is in the VUV range. In that case the temperature of the corona outside the spirals was lower (1-2 eV) than those analyzed from the S-300 device [27]. Referring to the Prague device, the wavelength of the emitted burst was estimated by using of the grazing impact reflection method, as illustrated in Sec.(5.3.9) [117]. Some of the studied results are presented in Fig.(6.14) and Fig.(6.15). A similar technique (but using a 200 μm plate of Si glass and/or 1.5 μm Al foil), was used in paper [120].

Figure 6.14: (a) Silver ratios. (b) Axial reflectivity

Figure 6.15: (a) Reflectivity. (b) Electron density as a function of the radius

Part of the analysis involved as well the determination of the axial voltage (Fig.(6.16) and the rate of expansion of diameter of the plasma as a function of time (Fig.(6.17).

Figure 6.16: Axial voltage reached as a function of the angle

Figure 6.17: Rate of expansion of diameter as a function of time

The burst of the radiation was reflected upon a silicon plate with roughness 1 nm and detected by a PIN diode. With Quadro camera diagnostics for window 596 nm the structure like helical ribbon of the discharge channel was observed with 2-3 threads, 400 – 700 μm diameter and length 2-3 mm. The whole current was conducted only through a narrow plasma column around the fiber, and the current channel past XUV burst conserved the shape of the original fiber between the electrodes. It means that the axis part of the fiber remained in a solid state. There was a long living plasma channel with a diameter $\sim 50 \mu\text{m}$, which could be due to a high conductivity of the plasma and by a strong magnetic confinement. Evidence that an important stabilizing factor for the plasma channel can be played by the solid remains of part of the fiber inside the channel was found [118–120].

A couple of different filters we used for the two PIN diodes for the determination of the energy distribution of the XUV radiation. Both diodes were located transversely with an azimuthal angle deflection of 45° . The PIN diodes were filtered with a combination of one Al 0.8 μm foils or one aluminized 1.5 μm mylar foil. The PIN diode signal obtained without any filter was compared with filtered signals, too. The differences in the intensities with foils

enabled to evaluate the emission in the transmission Al L-window of 17-90 nm and mylar O K transmission window of 4-6 nm. The energy in the mylar window reached 7% and the energy in the Al window 62 % of the total energy. The total emission energy detected with the PIN diodes was estimated to 160 mJ. The total energy given to the wire from the capacitors is 100 J. The mylar foil decreased the PIN diode signal to $1/10^{th}$, the Al foil to $1/8^{th}$. The emission had cylindrical symmetry and the energy, emitted transverse to the wire orientation, was three times higher than the emitted in the longitudinal direction [119]. An statistical analysis of the PIN diode records, as mentioned in [4,119], is shown in Fig.(6.18), Fig.(6.19), Fig.(6.20), and Fig.(6.21).

Figure 6.18: (a)FWHM for channel 3. (b) FWHM for channel 4

(a)

(b)

Figure 6.19: (a)Start for channel 3. (b) Start for channel 4

(a)

(b)

Figure 6.20: (a)Maximum for channel 3. (b) Maximum for channel 4

Figure 6.21: (a) Finish for channel 3. (b) Finish for channel 4

6.4.3 Saha Equation

Using Eq.(5.16) we have calculated the amount of ions related with the temperature and degrees of ionization, each related with a specific ionization potential. The weights $\sigma_z, / \sigma_{z+1}$ were $g_0 = 6, g_1 = 1, g_2 = 2, g_3 = 1, g_4 = 6, g_5 = 9$ [121]. From g_6 and onwards $g_n = 1$. In table (6.1) we have collected the most relevant results. In bold face are marked all those whose proportion n_{z+1}/n_z is close to one, therefore marking the probable degree of ionization. From there we have deduced the proportion of ions related with the detected concentration of electrons, as it can be seen in table (6.2).

Table 6.1: Dependence of the ionization proportion n_{z+1}/n_z on the electron temperature [eV] and the ionization potential U_i [eV]

$\frac{T \text{ eV} \rightarrow}{U_i \text{ eV} \downarrow}$	10	15	20	25	30
5.98	31.6176	70.8982	120.595	178.922	244.765
18.82	105.069	361.46	761.54	1284.67	1914.49
28.44	10.0375	47.5853	117.689	218.582	347.32
119.96	0.0127686	1.27902	14.5407	67.4421	197.253
153.71	0.000109229	0.0337021	0.672442	4.37093	16.0096

Table 6.2: Dependence of the proportion of ions/ n_e with respect to T [eV]

T [eV]	Ion/ n_e proportion
15	1/3
20	1/4
25	1/5
30	1/5

6.5 Estimation of Temperature and Density

Temperature and density were estimated from spectroscopy, Schlieren, shadow, PIN-diode and X-frame camera methods.

For example, shadow and Schlieren diagnostics based on the second harmonic emission of the neodymium laser (532 nm, pulse duration 8 ns) observing the plasma from the radial direction [115]. The detection of the X-ray emission was achieved through the usage of two absolutely calibrated and beryllium-filtered semiconductor PIN diodes providing temporal resolution of 1 ns and observing the plasma from both radial and axial directions.

Chapter 7

Dependence of Non-Ideality with n and T

The temperature at the surface of the corona was estimated to be around 30 eV from the PIN-diode and x-frame cameras diagnostics, and the temperature of the visible-light spirals could have been between 3-5 eV. That is to say, the maximum of the wavelength, according to the Planck curve, can be in UV, but most of the emission is in the visible range.

7.1 Dependence of Non-Ideality with N_D

In this section we will show that the inner layers of the z-pinch could be non-ideal for $N_D < 1$ which would make evident the non-ideal character of plasmas in the helical tube, allowing for long-range correlations and self-organization. We are now interested in proving that non-ideal conditions could have contributed to the formation of S.O. structures, from the reasonings about non-ideality developed in Sec.(3.6). We used Eq.(1.1) for the calculation of the Debye length, whose results are summarized in Table (7.1). Table (7.1) was used with Eq.(1.3) for the calculation of the number of particles in the Debye sphere. Such evaluation lead to Table (7.2).

From Table (7.2) we can estimate the limits of the electron temperature and the particle

density. Helical structures, observed inside of the plasma corona, are emitted only in visible light, and from spectroscopic records we know that the temperature should be between 3-5 eV and the electron density should be between $10^{27} - 10^{28} \text{m}^{-3}$. Taking these values, from Table (7.2) we realize that the number of particles in the Debye sphere is between 0.09-0.6. It makes evident the non-ideal nature of the plasma inside the visible helical tubes, allowing for self-organization.

At the temperature of 30 eV, the density of particles according to Table (7.1) could be $10^{26} - 10^{27} \text{m}^{-3}$. Table (7.2) says now that the number of particles in the Debye sphere is higher than one (in fact around 8-30), but this is not a non-ideal characteristic, according to Sec.(3.6).

Table 7.1: Dependence of the Debye length λ_D [m] on the electron temperature [eV] and the particle density [m^{-3}]

$\frac{T \text{ eV} \rightarrow}{n_e \text{ m}^{-3} \downarrow}$	1	3	5	10	30	50
10^{25}	2.34×10^{-9}	4.05×10^{-9}	5.23×10^{-9}	7.40×10^{-9}	1.28×10^{-8}	1.65×10^{-8}
10^{26}	7.40×10^{-10}	1.28×10^{-9}	1.65×10^{-9}	2.34×10^{-9}	4.05×10^{-9}	5.23×10^{-9}
10^{27}	2.34×10^{-10}	4.05×10^{-10}	5.23×10^{-10}	7.40×10^{-10}	1.28×10^{-9}	1.65×10^{-9}
10^{28}	7.40×10^{-11}	1.28×10^{-10}	1.65×10^{-10}	2.34×10^{-10}	4.05×10^{-10}	5.23×10^{-10}

Table 7.2: Dependence of the number of particles in the Debye sphere with electron density and temperature

$\frac{T \text{ eV} \rightarrow}{n_e \text{ m}^{-3} \downarrow}$	1	3	5	10	30	50
10^{25}	0.54	2.79	6	16.97	88.2	189.77
10^{26}	0.17	0.88	1.9	5.37	27.89	60.01
10^{27}	0.05	0.28	0.6	1.7	8.82	18.98
10^{28}	0.02	0.09	0.19	0.54	2.79	6

We can see that only the helical, visible structures could have had non-ideal plasmas,

which could have contributed to S.O.

We can infer that we probably have a non-ideal plasma with high correlation lengths and self-organization [29, 55] inside the helical structures, coexisting with plasma frozen by the magnetic field making the surface of the regular structures.

Chapter 8

Kinetic and Thermal Characteristics

We have evaluated some of the most relevant kinetic and thermal parameters related with the S.O. structures. For their calculation we have used some of the measurements and results from Sec.(6.1), Sec.(6.2), Sec.(6.3), Sec.(6.4.3), Sec.(6.5) Sec.(7) and Chap.(9). The central idea of this chapter is to show that the kinetic characteristics dependent on thermal effects are of a higher order than those which can be related to the intensity of the magnetic field B_φ (which is the result of the original current I_z . We intend to prove in Chap.(9) that thermal effects are dominated by the magnetic parameters, hence permitting the generation of S.O. structures. Also, wherever a kinetic characteristic is related directly with the magnetic field B_φ , particle movement got to be at most of the same order of magnitude as the magnetic forces which generated its movement.

8.1 Plasma Pressure and Kinetic Energy Density

8.1.1 Plasma Pressure

A rough estimation of the plasma pressure was made with the well-known Eq.(8.1)

$$p_{plasma} = nkT \tag{8.1}$$

which, for preliminary comparisons of this pressure against the magnetic pressure (see Chap.(9)), we have set $n = n_e$. In the next section we shall see a finer estimation, using the Saha equation. The results can be appreciated in table(8.1)

Table 8.1: Dependence of the kinetic pressure [Pa] on the electron temperature [eV] and the particle density [m^{-3}]

$\frac{T \text{ eV} \rightarrow}{n_e \text{ m}^{-3} \downarrow}$	3	5	10	30	50	100	300	500
10^{25}	5×10^6	8×10^6	2×10^7	5×10^7	8×10^7	2×10^8	5×10^8	8×10^8
10^{26}	4×10^7	8×10^7	2×10^8	5×10^8	8×10^8	2×10^9	5×10^9	8×10^9
10^{27}	1×10^8	8×10^8	2×10^9	5×10^9	8×10^9	2×10^{10}	5×10^{10}	8×10^{10}
10^{28}	4×10^8	8×10^9	2×10^{10}	5×10^{10}	8×10^{10}	2×10^{11}	5×10^{11}	8×10^{11}

8.1.2 Kinetic Energy Density

For actually comparing the magnetic and kinetic energy, we have studied the actual proportion of ions related with the detected concentration of electrons. We obtained the kinetic energy density with Eq.(8.2)

$$K.E.D. = n_I kT \quad (8.2)$$

where the concentration of ions n_I is actually $n = n(T)$ obtained from table (6.2) in Sec.(6.4.3). Table (8.2) collects the results.

Table 8.2: Dependence of $n_I kT$ with respect to T [eV]

T [eV]	$n_I(T)kT$ [J/m^{-3}]
15	4.4×10^8
20	4.4×10^8
25	4.4×10^8
30	5.29×10^8

Figure 8.1: Kinetic Energy. (a) Shot 17.1. (b) Shot 19.2

8.2 Plasma Frequency

Since we used Al in our experiments, for calculating the plasma frequency we use the corrected formula

$$\omega_p = 4\sqrt{n} \quad (8.3)$$

as explained in Sec.(1.2.3).

Table 8.3: Dependence of the plasma frequency ω_p on the particle density $n_e[\text{m}^{-3}]$

$n_e[\text{m}^{-3}]$	ω_p [Hz]
10^{25}	4.25×10^{12}
10^{26}	1.34×10^{13}
10^{27}	4.25×10^{13}
10^{28}	1.34×10^{14}

8.3 Electron Cyclotron Frequency (Ω_c)

For the estimation of Ω_c , we have used Eq.(8.4)

$$f_e = 28B \times 10^9[\text{GHz}] \tag{8.4}$$

A detailed exploration of this type of frequency, related with $B_\varphi(t)$ can be seen in Fig.(8.2)

Figure 8.2: Dependence of electron cyclotron frequency on the variation of B_φ with time. (a)for shot 17.1. (b) for shot 19.2

The cyclotron frequency, related with the most important $\mathbf{B}$ values observed, is depicted in table(8.4).

Table 8.4: Dependence of the electron cyclotron frequency (Ω_c , [Hz]) on the intensity of the magnetic field $\mathbf{B}$ [T]

$\mathbf{B}$ [T]	Ω_c [Hz]
10	2.8×10^{11}
30	8.40×10^{11}
50	1.40×10^{12}
70	1.96×10^{12}
100	2.80×10^{12}

8.4 Thermal velocities

All the velocities used in this work (the acoustic velocity of plasma v_z , the thermal velocity of electrons v_{te} and v_{rms}) depend somehow on the square root of temperature, although some are rather related with the ion's mass and others with the electron's mass.

8.4.1 Acoustic Velocity

The acoustic velocity of plasma was determined by Eq.(8.5)

$$v_z = \left(\frac{kT_e}{M} \right)^{1/2} \quad (8.5)$$

and its relation with the different values of electron temperatures T_e used in this work is depicted in Fig.(8.3).

Figure 8.3: Dependence of the acoustic velocity with the variation of T_e

8.4.2 Heat (Thermal) Velocity of Electrons

The dependence of change of thermal velocity of electrons with temperature (Fig.(8.4)), was obtained by means of Eq.(8.6) [19]

$$v_{te} = \left(\frac{2kT_e}{m} \right)^{1/2} \quad (8.6)$$

Figure 8.4: Heat velocity of electrons

8.4.3 Velocity root-mean square (v_{rms})

We consider $kT = E$ so that Eq.(8.7a) and Eq.(8.7a) are valid

$$v_{rms} = \left(\frac{3E}{M_{Al}} \right)^{1/2} \tag{8.7a}$$

$$v_{rms} = \left(\frac{3E}{m} \right)^{1/2} \tag{8.7b}$$

Table(8.5) collects the values used for the calculation of the Larmor radius.

Table 8.5: Dependence of the velocity root-mean-square with T

T [J]	T [eV]	v_{rms} ions	v_{rms} electrons
4.8×10^{-19}	3	5.65×10^3	1.26×10^6
8×10^{-19}	5	7.29×10^3	1.62×10^6
1.6×10^{-18}	10	1.03×10^4	2.3×10^6
4.8×10^{-18}	30	1.79×10^4	3.98×10^6

The v_{rms} was the velocity used for the calculation of the Larmor radius.

8.5 Larmor Radius

For the determination of the Larmor radius it was used Eq.(8.8a) and Eq.(8.8b), for the Larmor radius of electrons and Al ions respectively. It was used v_{rms} as estimated in Sec.(8.4.3). The collection of results are observed from Fig.(8.5) to Fig.(8.12).

$$r_{L(e)} = \frac{mv_{\perp}}{eB_{\phi}} \tag{8.8a}$$

$$r_{L(Al)} = \frac{M_{Al}v_{\perp}}{eB_{\phi}} \tag{8.8b}$$

Figure 8.5: Larmor radius of electrons, 3 eV. (a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

Figure 8.6: Larmor radius of electrons, 5 eV. (a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

Figure 8.7: Larmor radius of electrons, 10 eV. (a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

Figure 8.8: Larmor radius of electrons, 30 eV. (a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

Figure 8.9: Larmor radius of ions, 3 eV. (a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

(a)

(b)

Figure 8.10: Larmor radius of ions, 5 eV. (a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

(a)

(b)

Figure 8.11: Larmor radius of ions, 10 eV. (a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

Figure 8.12: Larmor radius of ions, 30 eV. (a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

8.6 Alfvén Velocity

Using Eq.(1.9) we have determined the dependence of this velocity with respect to $B_\phi(t)$, as it is summarized in Fig.(8.13) and table(8.6). Compare the velocities obtained for this section with those in Fig.(6.4).

Figure 8.13: Dependence of Alfvén velocity with the variation of B_ϕ in time.(a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

Table 8.6: Dependence of the Alfvén velocity on the magnetic field B [T] and the concentration of electrons n_e [m^{-3}]

$\frac{n_e [\text{m}^{-3}] \rightarrow}{B [\text{T}] \downarrow}$	10^{25}	10^{26}	10^{27}	10^{28}
10	1.33×10^4	4.20×10^3	1.33×10^3	4.20×10^2
30	3.98×10^4	1.26×10^4	3.98×10^3	1.26×10^3
50	6.64×10^4	2.10×10^4	6.64×10^3	2.10×10^3
70	9.29×10^4	2.94×10^4	9.29×10^3	2.94×10^3
100	1.33×10^5	4.20×10^4	1.33×10^4	4.20×10^3

8.7 Collision Frequencies

Collision frequencies are important to decide how close (or how far) a plasma is from non-ideality. An ideal plasma is *collisionless* even when $n \rightarrow \infty$ [21]. The used formulas come from the book of Francis Chen [19].

8.7.1 Electron-Ion

The results presented in table (8.7) were obtained with Eq.(8.9).

$$\nu_{ei} = 1.5 \times 10^{-12} \frac{n \ln \Lambda}{T_{[eV]}^{3/2}} \quad (8.9)$$

Table 8.7: Dependence of the collision frequency electron-ion [No. of collisions $\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] on the temperature [eV] and the particle density n_e [m^{-3}]

$\frac{T [eV] \rightarrow}{n_e [\text{m}^{-3}] \downarrow}$	1	3	5	10	30	50
10^{25}	1.50×10^{14}	2.89×10^{13}	1.34×10^{13}	4.74×10^{12}	9.13×10^{11}	4.24×10^{11}
10^{26}	1.50×10^{15}	2.89×10^{14}	1.34×10^{14}	4.74×10^{13}	9.13×10^{12}	4.24×10^{12}
10^{27}	1.50×10^{16}	2.89×10^{15}	1.34×10^{15}	4.74×10^{14}	9.13×10^{13}	4.24×10^{13}
10^{28}	1.50×10^{17}	2.89×10^{16}	1.34×10^{16}	4.74×10^{15}	9.13×10^{14}	4.24×10^{14}

8.7.2 Electron-Electron

In order to estimate the collision frequencies electron-electron presented in table(8.8) we could use Eq.(8.10).

$$\nu_{ee} = 3 \times 10^{-12} \frac{n \ln \Lambda}{T_{[eV]}^{3/2}} \quad (8.10)$$

Table 8.8: Dependence of the collision frequency electron-electron [No. of collisions·s⁻¹] on the temperature [eV] and the particle particle density n_e [m⁻³]

$\frac{T \text{ eV} \rightarrow}{n_e \text{ m}^{-3} \downarrow}$	1	3	5	10	30	50
10 ²⁵	3×10 ¹⁴	5.77×10 ¹³	2.68×10 ¹³	9.49×10 ¹²	1.83×10 ¹²	8.49×10 ¹¹
10 ²⁶	3×10 ¹⁵	5.77×10¹⁴	2.68×10¹⁴	9.49×10¹³	1.83×10¹³	8.49×10 ¹²
10 ²⁷	3×10 ¹⁶	5.77×10¹⁵	2.68×10¹⁵	9.49×10¹⁴	1.83×10¹⁴	8.49×10 ¹³
10 ²⁸	3×10 ¹⁷	5.77×10 ¹⁶	2.68×10 ¹⁶	9.49×10 ¹⁵	1.83×10 ¹⁵	8.49×10 ¹⁴

8.7.3 Ion-Ion

For the estimation of collision frequencies ion-ion (table(8.9)) we have used Eq.(8.11)

$$\nu_{ii} = Z^4 \left(\frac{m}{M_{Al}} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{T_e}{T_i} \right)^{3/2} \nu_{ee} \quad (8.11)$$

where T_e/T_i was taken ~ 1 .

Table 8.9: Dependence of the collision frequency ion-ion [No. of collisions $\cdot$ s $^{-1}$] on the temperature [eV] and the particle particle density n_e [m $^{-3}$]

$\frac{T \text{ eV} \rightarrow}{n_e \text{ m}^{-3} \downarrow}$	1	3	5	10	30	50
10^{25}	3.85×10^{16}	7.41×10^{15}	3.44×10^{15}	1.22×10^{15}	2.34×10^{14}	1.09×10^{14}
10^{26}	3.85×10^{17}	7.41×10^{16}	3.44×10^{16}	1.22×10^{16}	2.34×10^{15}	1.09×10^{15}
10^{27}	3.85×10^{18}	7.41×10^{17}	3.44×10^{17}	1.22×10^{17}	2.34×10^{16}	1.09×10^{16}
10^{28}	3.85×10^{19}	7.41×10^{18}	3.44×10^{18}	1.22×10^{18}	2.34×10^{17}	1.09×10^{17}

8.8 Mean Free Path

For the estimation of the mean free path, we have used Eq.(8.12)

$$\lambda_{ei} \approx \lambda_{ee} \approx \lambda_{ii} = 4.5 \times 10^{17} \frac{T_{[eV]}^2}{n \ln \Lambda} \quad (8.12)$$

Table 8.10: Dependence of the mean free path [m] on the temperature [eV] and the particle density $n_e[\text{m}^{-3}]$

$\frac{T \text{ eV} \rightarrow}{n_e \text{ m}^{-3} \downarrow}$	1	3	5	10	30	50
10^{25}	4.50×10^{-9}	4.05×10^{-8}	1.13×10^{-7}	4.50×10^{-7}	4.05×10^{-6}	1.13×10^{-5}
10^{26}	4.50×10^{-10}	4.05×10^{-9}	1.13×10^{-8}	4.50×10^{-8}	4.05×10^{-7}	1.13×10^{-6}
10^{27}	4.50×10^{-11}	4.05×10^{-10}	1.13×10^{-9}	4.50×10^{-9}	4.05×10^{-8}	1.13×10^{-7}
10^{28}	4.50×10^{-12}	4.05×10^{-11}	1.13×10^{-10}	4.50×10^{-10}	4.05×10^{-9}	1.13×10^{-8}

Chapter 9

Magnetic Characteristics of S.O. Structures

9.1 General Assumptions

Apart from the assumptions that have been mentioned along this work, we can still mention that for the evaluation of the magnetic characteristics we considered that

- The whole discharge current is located inside those self-organized structures.
- We think that the repeatability of the helical structures in the S-300 is related with a similar situation as described in Sec.(6.4.2), i.e., that the fact that the central part of the fiber was still in a solid state was an stabilizing factor for the plasma channel.
- For the helical structure, the pinching azimuthal magnetic pressure is equalized by the sum of the inside-generated axial magnetic pressure and of the kinetic pressure of the plasma, making each of these last half of the total contribution, as in Eq.(2.4).
- The magnetic field behaves linearly with the current and inversely proportional to the radius.
- The current may have a topology as shown in Fig.(9.1) and the magnetic fields B_ϕ and B_z behave with a topology as it can be seen in Fig.(9.2). This last assumption is based on the characteristics of the observed structures given by the different diagnostic methods,

so that Eqn.(2.4) may hold.

9.1.1 Topological models

We think that a plausible model for the topology of the current and of the magnetic field, which can help on the description of both visible spirals and X-ray ring structures can be appreciated in Fig.(9.1) and Fig.(9.2). Compare these figures with Fig.(6.1(a)) and Fig.(6.1(b)).

Figure 9.1: Topology of the current in spirals and rings.

Figure 9.2: Topology of the magnetic field in spirals and rings.

Helical structures could be produced due to generation of the B_z magnetic field. This phenomena in plasma could be explained by the dynamo effect, as we have seen in Sec.(4.2).

9.2 Intensity of the Magnetic Fields

The current (Sec.(6.3)), with the radius data (Sec.(6.2)), was used for obtaining the values of the magnetic field B_φ at the boundary of the plasma using Eq.(4.3). The average magnetic field inside the plasma was calculated according to Eq.(5.9). In the moment of the XUV-pulse we had the following parameters for B_φ :

- In the shot 17.1 the local maximum of the magnetic field at 100 ns was calculated as 150 Teslas for the neck zone, and of 70 Teslas for the node zone. The average magnetic field was about 100 Teslas for the neck and 50 Teslas for the node (at 100 ns).

- In the shot 19.2 the local maximum of magnetic field at 100 ns was about 190 Teslas for the neck and 90 Teslas for the node. The attained average magnetic field was about 40 Teslas for the neck zone and about 20 Teslas for the node zone. A detailed evolution for B_φ intensity in time is shown in Fig.(9.3)

Figure 9.3: Dependence of the intensity of the Magnetic Field B_φ against time and its average $\bar{B}_\varphi$.(a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

We could also calculate the intensity of the axial magnetic field B_Z , by considering the fact that in the investigated spirals, the current tubes make 1.5 turns, and knowing the

formula about slopes in spirals given in [15], we can directly say that

$$I_z = 1.5 \times I_\varphi$$

which is valid at least until 100 ns, when we are sure that there was an helical-like plasma structure.

Furthermore, we actually calculated the average magnetic field B_Z with the formula for the magnetic field of a circular loop [9]

$$B_Z(z) = \frac{\mu_0 \cdot I \cdot r^2}{2 \cdot (z^2 + r^2)^{3/2}} \quad (9.1)$$

where z stands for the finite thickness of the loop, which in our case will stand for the length of the plasma cylinder.

Using in concrete a maximal plasma length of 10 mm, we integrate Eq.(9.1) as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{B}_Z &= \frac{1}{10 \times 10^{-3}} \times 2 \times \int_0^{10 \times 10^{-3}/2} B(z) dz \\ &= \frac{100\mu_0 \cdot I}{(1 + 4 \times 10^4 \cdot r^2)^{1/2}} \end{aligned} \quad (9.2)$$

By using Eq.(9.2) we could compare the time evolution of $\bar{B}_Z$ with that of $\bar{B}_\varphi$, as it is possible to see in Fig.(9.4).

As we could see in Sec.(9.1.1), B_Z or more precisely $\bar{B}_Z$ is an important factor for the geometrical existence of helical structures and ringed structures. It is only after the pinch phase that the transformations of $\bar{B}_Z$ contribute to the destruction of S.O.

Figure 9.4: Dependence of the intensity of the magnetic fields $\bar{B}_\phi$ and $\bar{B}_Z$ with respect to time.(a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

9.3 Magnetic Pressure

We can also consider the magnetic pressure equal to the magnetic energy density. Its calculation could be obtained using Eq.(9.3), and the knowledge of Sec.(9.2)

$$Pressure(B_\phi) = \frac{\bar{B}_\phi^2}{2\mu_0} \quad (9.3)$$

In the moment of the XUV-pulse emission at 100 ns, the corona in the neck region reached for the average magnetic azimuthal pressure a pressure of $\approx 5 \times 10^9$ Pa. In Fig.(9.5) we can observe the whole evolution in time of the magnetic pressure (magnetic energy density).

9.3.1 Comparison of Magnetic and Kinetic Pressures

Helical Structures

We have seen in Sec.(2.4) and Sec.(9.3) how B_Z contributes to the helical structure generation. In concrete, since we know that the average magnetic azimuthal pressure at 100 ns

Figure 9.5: Dependence of the magnetic pressure (magnetic energy density) coming from the azimuthal magnetic field B_ϕ against time.(a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

was about 5×10^9 Pa (Fig.(9.5)), the upper boundary for dynamic pressure $\sum nkT$ can be estimated from the magnetic azimuthal pressure.

For the generation of the helical structures we assume that part of this pressure must be compensated by an axial magnetic pressure B_Z . For simple estimations let us use Eq.(2.4). We will suppose that the kinetic pressure, at its maximum, can be equal to the axial magnetic pressure, so that the kinetic pressure would be equal or even lower than 2.5×10^9 Pa . In table (8.1) we have set in bold face all those pressures close to these values.

Ringed Structures

Calculations based on the Saha equation (Eq.(5.16)), leded us to table(8.2). For this table, we have thought that the temperature in the necks and nodes is different, for they radiate differently. The temperature before and after the pinch phase (at 100 ns) could be different as well. For example, after the pinch phase the plasma in general gets colder. We have therefore assumed the temperature models as presented in table (9.1)

According to table(8.2), the kinetic energy density (or plasma pressure) in the ringed

Table 9.1: Temperature models for S.O.. The temperatures are in the sequence *before pinch-pinch itself (XUV pulse)-after pinch*

Shot(T [eV]) $\rightarrow$ zone $\downarrow$	17.1	19.2
Neck	20 – 30 – 20	25 – 30 – 25
Node	15 – 15 – 15	20 – 25 – 20

structure is at least one order of magnitude smaller than the magnetic pressure, as it can be seen in Fig.(9.5).

Ratio Plasma Pressure/Magnetic Pressure (β)

For deciding whether the magnetic pressure is higher than the thermal energy density, we can combine the results of table(8.2) and of Fig.(9.5), for achieving Fig.(9.6).

Figure 9.6: Dependence of β with time.(a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2.

9.4 MHD Considerations

9.4.1 Diffusion of the Magnetic Field into Plasma

Using Eq.(1.10) (Spitzer formula), we estimated different values of resistivity (table(9.2)), according to the temperature model mentioned in Sec.(9.3.1). We know that $\gamma = 1/\eta$, therefore we may use table(9.2) for the calculation of the time for diffusion of the magnetic field with Eq.(2.8). The results are depicted in table(9.3).

Table 9.2: Dependence of resistivity on temperature

T [eV]	η [ohm metres]
15	1.38228×10^{-5}
20	8.66615×10^{-6}
25	6.02783×10^{-6}
30	4.53171×10^{-6}

Table 9.3: Dependence of the diffusion time of the magnetic field on temperature

T [eV]	t_{DB} [ns]
15	0.91
20	1.45
25	2.08
30	2.8

9.4.2 Freezing of Magnetic Lines into Plasma

If the typical velocity of the increase of the corona diameter is $\sim 10^4 \text{m} \cdot \text{sec}^{-1}$ (Sec.(6.2)), so the flow of particles in the surface of the regular structures is frozen into the magnetic fields, because being the temperature in the regular structures of the XUV region as high

as 30 eV, the velocity of the increase of the corona diameter should be higher, as illustrated in Sec.(8.4).

According to Eq.(2.11), we need the plasma dimensions for calculating the lower boundary for the time that the magnetic field may hold the plasma into the shape which depends on that dimension. Freezing time for the ringed structure depends on its thickness ($100\mu\text{m}$) and taking the Alfvén velocity as $5.5 \times 10^3 \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, we obtain that it is at least 18.18 ns. Therefore, conductivity should be higher than the predicted by the Spitzer formula. We think that the conductivity (for S.O. structures with a duration between 20-40 ns) should be between $1.59155 \times 10^6 \leq \gamma \leq 3.1831 \times 10^6 \text{ siemens} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$.

9.4.3 Reynolds Magnetic Number

Using Eq.(2.12) we come again to realize in table(9.4) that conductivity should be higher, so that the freezing of magnetic lines into plasma could dominate over the diffusion of magnetic field, as they seem to do for S.O.

Table 9.4: Dependence of the Reynolds magnetic number on temperature

T [eV]	Ω_c [Hz]
15	0.05
20	0.079753
25	0.11466
30	0.152514

9.5 Magnetic Energy

The magnetic energy was evaluated by Eq.(9.4)

$$E(B) = \frac{\bar{B}_\varphi^2}{2\mu_0} \times volume \quad (9.4)$$

The temporal evolution of $E(B)$ could be achieved by combining the data from Fig.(6.7) and Fig.(9.5). The result of it is illustrated in Fig.(9.7).

Figure 9.7: Total magnetic Energy.(a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2.

9.6 Equilibrium Magnetic Radius r_B

Let us define an equilibrium ratio of the plasma pressure with the magnetic pressure as

$$\beta_{equilibrium} = 1$$

The magnetic field corresponding to this ratio (which we shall call $B_\varphi(1)$) is

$$B_\varphi(1) = \sqrt{nkT \times 2\mu_0} \quad (9.5)$$

And the results are summarized in table(9.5).

Since $B_\varphi(1) = \mu_0 I_z / 2\pi r$ therefore we may define an equilibrium magnetic radius as

$$r_B = \frac{\mu_0 \cdot I(z)}{B_\varphi \cdot 2\pi i} \quad (9.6)$$

Table 9.5: Dependence of $B_\varphi(1)$ on temperature

T [eV]	$B_\varphi(1)$ [T]
15	33.27
20	33.27
25	33.27
30	36.45

from which we obtained Fig.(9.8), illustrating at 100 ns a difference in radius between neck and node, which may correspond geometrically to the observed ringed structure (Fig.(6.1)(b))

(a)

(b)

Figure 9.8: Dependence of r_B with time.(a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

Chapter 10

Decrease of Entropy for S.O.

Central to S.O. is the expulsion of useless energy of a system, as we have seen in Sec.(3.5.1) or Fig.(3.1). We are assuming here that the S.O. structures, which have been appearing during the pinch phase, can be considered as open systems, for they are part of the initial pulse of current. It is their surroundings (in this case, the implosion chamber) which enclose them and receive the emitted particles and radiation, thence decreasing the entropy of the imploding plasma, contributing in an essential way to S.O. We have analyzed mainly the expulsion of entropy for the ringed structures, and the overall expulsion of entropy as estimated from the detected radiation and temperature.

10.1 Energy Input

10.1.1 Resistance

We begin with the estimation of the resistance by Eq.(10.1)

$$R = \frac{length \times \eta}{area} \quad (10.1)$$

where the $area = area(t)$ is taken as the cross-sectional area of the ringed structure, and the variation over time was obtained from the data of the variation of the radius as in

Fig.(6.3). We have then used Eq.(10.2).

$$area = \pi \times (r^2 - (r - 100 \mu\text{m})^2) \quad (10.2)$$

We recall from Fig.(6.2) that $100 \mu\text{m}$ is the approximate thickness of the crust which forms the ringed structure.

We can now observe the results of this evaluation in Fig.(10.1)

Figure 10.1: Variation of the resistance with time.(a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

10.1.2 Joule Heating

With the knowledge of Fig.(10.1) we are now in the position of estimating the variation of the input of energy to the system by using Eq.(10.3), which is the Joule (or otherwise called *Ohmic*, since it involves the resistance) heating [8].

$$Q_J = I^2 \times R \times t \quad (10.3)$$

The result of this evaluation is shown in Fig.(10.2).

Figure 10.2: Variation of the input of energy (through Joule -Ohmic- heating) into the plasma with time.(a) Shot 17.1.(b) Shot 19.2

10.2 Entropy Expulsion

10.2.1 Radiated Energy

Although the observed pinches are optically thick, we consider the emission *from the boundary*. Therefore we may assume the Stephan-Boltzmann law (Eq.(10.4)), which in this case includes the area of radiation. We have also considered only half of the axial area of the ringed structures, since we can observe in Fig.(6.1) that most of the radiation comes from the neck. We have then estimated the variation of the radiated energy in time (Fig.(10.3)).

$$Q_{S-B} = \sigma \cdot T^4 \times \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \cdot 2\pi \cdot r \cdot 8 \cdot 10^{-3}t \quad (10.4)$$

where $8 \cdot 10^{-3}$ is the length of the ringed structures, as in Fig.(6.1).

Figure 10.3: Variation of the emitted energy (mostly from the neck) with time.(a) Shot 17.1. (b) Shot 19.2.

10.2.2 Total Decrease of Entropy

Combining the knowledge of the kinetic energy from the expelled particles in Fig.(8.1) (we assume that most particles come from the nodes, hence only half of the axial area may contribute substantially to the thermal energy of the expelled particles), and the radiated energy from Fig.(10.3), we can now apply the well-known Eq.(10.5) for evaluating the total decrease of entropy [8]. We have applied the model of temperatures as shown in table(9.1). The results are seen in Fig.(10.4).

$$\Delta S = \frac{dQ_{S-B}}{T} \quad (10.5)$$

We can appreciate that at the pinch phase there was an important increase in the expelled entropy.

Moreover, from the PIN diode records it was measured a total radiated energy $E \approx 10^2$ [J], and from the spectrometric records it was measured a temperature $T \approx 3.48 \times$

(a)

(b)

Figure 10.4: Dependence of the expulsion of entropy ΔS with time. (a) Shot 17.1. (b) Shot 19.2.

10^5 [K], from which we have deduced that the total decrease of entropy detected could have been about $S \approx 2.87 \times 10^{-4}$ [J/K].

Chapter 11

Conclusions

- It was found that a major contributor, for self-organization to occur, was the dominance of electro-magnetic energy over the kinetic energy.

- The helical-like structures were found to be high-density ($n_e \approx 10^{27}$), low-temperature (3-5 eV) plasmas (non-ideal), where the electrostatic energy dominates over the thermal energy.

- In the coma of the Al wire electron the temperatures are relatively low (5 – 30eV) and density relatively high ($10^{27} - 10^{28}\text{m}^{-3}$). Then the obtained values of the number of particles in the Debye sphere in the helical structures in the visible region should be between 0.09 – 0.6, corresponding to a non-ideal plasma with high correlation lengths and self-organization. The regular, ring structures in the soft x-ray region had a relatively high number of particles in the Debye sphere (8-30), therefore non-ideality does not contribute for self-organization in the ringed structures, but it is rather the result of the presence of a magnetic field that freezes the plasma into the surface of the observed regular ring structures in the external layer of the corona.

- For both, helical and ringed structures, the dominance of magnetic energy density over the thermal energy was important for their existence. In the case of the ringed-like,

higher temperature (≈ 30 eV) plasma structures, electrostatic energy could not contribute significantly for self-organization, but the magnetic energy was found to be the decisive factor for the shape it acquired. Ringed structures were found to have a density of an order of magnitude ($n_e = 10^{26}$) lower than the spiral structures, and in average we had $n_e = 5.5 \times 10^{26}$.

- The spiral shape could have been produced because of two major factors:

(1) The possibility that the dynamo effect could have produced an azimuthal and an axial magnetic field.

(2) The fact that part of the original Al wire remained during the pinch phase in solid state, hence possibly permitting the plasma close to the wire to wind around it.

- Still another major factor for self-organization was the high particle density ($\langle n_e \rangle = 5.5 \times 10^{26}$).

- There is a positive strong correlation between the expulsion of entropy and the persistence in the existence of self-organized structures.

- Evaluations related with magnetohydrodynamic equations lead us to think that conductivity should have been at least one order of magnitude higher than the one predicted by the Spitzer formula.

-

At 100 ns the following parameters were observed:

1) Shot 99.05.17.1: $v_{neck} = 10 \times 10^4 \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, $v_{node} = 8 \times 10^4 \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. $B_\phi(\text{neck}) = 150\text{T}$, $B_\phi(\text{node}) = 70\text{T}$. $\bar{B}_\phi(\text{neck}) = 100\text{T}$, $\bar{B}_\phi(\text{node}) = 50\text{T}$. $p_{\bar{B}_\phi} = 4.28 \times 10^9 \text{Pa}$

2) Shot 99.05.19.2: $v_{neck} = 6 \times 10^4 \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, $v_{node} = 4 \times 10^4 \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. $B_\phi(\text{neck}) = 190\text{T}$, $B_\phi(\text{node}) = 90\text{T}$. $\bar{B}_\phi(\text{neck}) = 40\text{T}$, $\bar{B}_\phi(\text{node}) = 20\text{T}$. $p_{\bar{B}_\phi} = 6.3 \times 10^8 \text{Pa}$

Appendix A

Used Formulas (MKS)

Eq.(1.1) Debye Length [m]

$$\lambda_D = \left(\frac{\epsilon_0 kT}{ne^2} \right)^{1/2}$$

Eq.(1.3) Number of Particles in the Debye Sphere [None]

$$N_D = n \cdot \frac{4}{3} \pi \lambda_D^3$$

Eq.(1.8) Plasma Frequency for Al [Hz]

$$\omega_{pAl} = 4\sqrt{n}$$

Eq.(1.9) Alfvén Velocity [m · s⁻¹]

$$v_A = \frac{B}{(\mu_0 \rho_{Al})^{1/2}}$$

Eq.(1.10) Resistivity [ohm meters]

$$\eta \approx \frac{e^2 m^{1/2}}{16\pi \epsilon_0^2 (kT_e)^{3/2}} \cdot \ln \Lambda$$

Eq.(2.4) Pinch Equilibrium [Pa]

$$\frac{\bar{B}_\phi^2}{2\mu_0} = nkT + \frac{\bar{B}_Z^2}{2\mu_0}$$

Eq.(2.8) Diffusion Time of $\mathbf{B}$ [s]

$$\Delta t = \mu\gamma L^2$$

Eq.(2.11) Freezing Time of $\mathbf{B}$ [s]

$$\Delta t = \frac{L}{V}$$

Eq.(2.12) Reynolds Magnetic Number [None]

$$R_M = \mu\gamma VL$$

Eq.(4.3) Intensity of the Azimuthal Magnetic Field [T]

$$B_\varphi = \frac{\mu_0 I_z}{2\pi r}$$

Eq.(5.1) Velocity of Expansion of the Corona Diameter (using the streak camera record) [$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]

$$v = \frac{r_{i+1} - r_i}{t_{i+1} - t_i}$$

Eq.(5.9) Average Azimuthal Magnetic Field [T]

$$\bar{B}_\varphi = \frac{\mu_0 I_z}{3\pi R}$$

Eq.(5.16) Saha Equation for the Degree of Ionization [None]

$$\frac{n_{z+1} n_e}{n_z} = \frac{\sigma_{z+1}}{\sigma_z} \cdot 6 \times 10^{27} (kT_{[eV]})^{3/2} \cdot e^{\frac{E_i}{kT_{[eV]}}}$$

Eq.(5.17) Wavelength Dependent on Angle on Reflectivity [nm]

$$\alpha[^\circ] \approx \lambda$$

Eq.(6.1) Volume of Ringed Structure [m^3]

$$Volume = 2 \times l \times \pi \times r \times dx$$

Eq.(8.1) Plasma Pressure [Pa]

$$p_{plasma} = \sum nkT$$

Eq.(8.2) Kinetic Energy Density [Pa or J/m^3]

$$K.E.D. = n_I kT$$

- Eq.(8.4) Electron Cyclotron Frequency [GHz]
- $$\Omega_c = 28B \times 10^9$$
- Eq.(8.5) Acoustic Velocity [m · s⁻¹]
- $$v_z = \left(\frac{kT_e}{M} \right)^{1/2}$$
- Eq.(8.6) Heat (Thermal) Velocity of Electrons [m · s⁻¹]
- $$v_{te} = \left(\frac{2kT_e}{m} \right)^{1/2}$$
- Eq.(8.7a) Velocity Root-Mean Square for Ions [m · s⁻¹]
- $$v_{rms} = \left(\frac{3E}{M_{Al}} \right)^{1/2}$$
- Eq.(8.7b) Velocity Root-Mean Square for Electrons [m · s⁻¹]
- $$v_{rms} = \left(\frac{3E}{m} \right)^{1/2}$$
- Eq.(8.8a) Larmor Radius for Electrons [m]
- $$r_{L(e)} = \frac{mv_{\perp}}{eB_{\varphi}}$$
- Eq.(8.8b) Larmor Radius for Al Ions [m]
- $$r_{L(Al)} = \frac{M_{Al}v_{\perp}}{eB_{\varphi}}$$
- Eq.(8.9) Collision Frequencies Electron-Ion [No. of collisions·s⁻¹]
- $$\nu_{ei} = 1.5 \times 10^{-12} \frac{n \ln \Lambda}{T_{[eV]}^{3/2}}$$
- Eq.(8.10) Collision Frequencies Electron-Electron [No. of collisions·s⁻¹]
- $$\nu_{ee} = 3 \times 10^{-12} \frac{n \ln \Lambda}{T_{[eV]}^{3/2}}$$

Eq.(8.11) Collision Frequencies Ion-Ion [No. of collisions·s⁻¹]

$$\nu_{ii} = Z^4 \left(\frac{m}{M_{At}} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{T_e}{T_i} \right)^{3/2} \nu_{ee}$$

Eq.(8.12) Mean Free Path [m]

$$\lambda_{ei} \approx \lambda_{ee} \approx \lambda_{ii} = 4.5 \times 10^{17} \frac{T_{[eV]}^2}{n \ln \Lambda}$$

Eq.(9.2) Average Axial Magnetic Field [T]

$$\bar{B}_Z = \frac{100\mu_0 \cdot I}{(1 + 4 \times 10^4 \cdot r^2)^{1/2}}$$

Eq.(9.3) Azimuthal Magnetic Pressure [Pa or J/m⁻³]

$$Pressure(B_\varphi) = \frac{\bar{B}_\varphi^2}{2\mu_0}$$

Eq.(9.4) Magnetic Energy [J]

$$E(B) = \frac{\bar{B}_\varphi^2}{2\mu_0} \times volume$$

Eq.(9.5) Equilibrium Magnetic Field [T]

$$B_\varphi(1) = \sqrt{nkt \times 2\mu_0}$$

Eq.(9.6) Equilibrium Magnetic Radius [m]

$$r_B = \frac{\mu_0 \cdot I(z)}{B_\varphi \cdot 2Pi}$$

Eq.(10.1) Resistance [ohms]

$$R = \frac{length \times \eta}{area}$$

Eq.(10.2) Cross-Sectional Area for Ringed Structures [m⁻²]

$$area = \pi \times (r^2 - (r - 100 \mu\text{m})^2)$$

Eq.(10.3) Joule Heating [J]

$$Q_J = I^2 \times R \times t$$

Eq.(10.4) Stephan-Boltzmann Radiation [J]

$$Q_{S-B} = \sigma \cdot T^4 \times \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \cdot 2\pi \cdot r \cdot 8 \cdot 10^{-3}t$$

Eq.(10.5) Decrease of Entropy [J/K]

$$\Delta S = \frac{dQ_{S-B}}{T}$$

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